

Chair of Mechanical Engineering

Master's Thesis

Tribological characterization of valvetrain
ball/socket-contacts based on a tribometric
model testing system

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Abstract

The demand for higher efficiency and less emissions in combustion engines requires the use of low-viscosity engine oils in order to reduce friction losses. In addition, certain oil additives must be reduced to meet novel environmental regulations. This leads to increased wear on engine components which were uncritical in the past. Especially at ball/socket-contacts in valvetrains, wear is critical because it affects the valve clearance and consequently the gas exchange, which can lead to efficiency losses, increase in emissions and engine damage. Currently, engine tests with a run time of several days are used to investigate the tribological performance of valvetrain components. To reduce costs and testing duration, a model testing system is demanded.

Therefore, a test setup on a rotary tribometer was designed, where various ball and socket specimens cut out from engine valvetrain components can be tested within one day. With the test setup's modular structure it is possible to vary different specimens, their assembly positions, lubrication systems and motion. A suitable test program to simulate the running conditions was developed, which is based on a start-stop cycle, and an appropriate data evaluation was programmed. The results of an accompanying optical analysis and gravimetric wear measurements are compared with engine tests. Changing the axis of rotation due to machine settings requires an adjustment of speed and load to match the same mild abrasive wear mechanism as observed in engine parts. As tests with fresh oil did not cause significant wear to make meaningful statements in terms of oil effectiveness, an artificial oil aging process was performed by adding abrasive particles or a soot surrogate to fresh oil.

It was shown that the geometric difference in sockets has a big influence on reproducibility as it supports the build-up of a potential load-bearing oil film. Tests with used engine oil proved that, with this test setup, causing significant wear in a moderate time is possible. Furthermore, it was shown that, depending on their concentration, abrasive particles increase the coefficient of friction, which can lead to seizure, but do not increase mild abrasive wear in the investigated components. Adding a soot surrogate significantly increases wear. According to literature, this is due to chemical interaction of the oil additive zinc dialkyldithiophosphate with soot. For the purpose of validation, tests with various oils with well-known engine performance were conducted. It was shown that an oil with low wear in the engine also shows low wear in model tests using artificial oil aging. Consequently, the developed test procedure provides a good tool for gaining deeper understanding and tribosystem-screening of ball/socket-contacts.

Kurzfassung

Höhere Wirkungsgrade und geringere Emissionen in Verbrennungsmotoren erfordern niedrigviskose Motoröle, um Reibungsverluste zu reduzieren. Zusätzlich müssen bestimmte Öl-Additive reduziert werden, um neue Umweltbestimmungen zu erfüllen. Dies führt zu höherem Verschleiß an Motorkomponenten, die bisher eine unkritische Verschleißcharakteristik zeigten. Vor allem an Kugelgelenken in Ventiltrieben wirkt sich Verschleiß sehr negativ aus, da dadurch das Ventilspiel und folglich der Gasaustausch beeinflusst werden. Dies kann zur Reduktion des Wirkungsgrades, höheren Emissionen und Motorschäden führen. Derzeit werden Motortests mit einer Laufzeit von mehreren Tagen durchgeführt, um das tribologische Verhalten von Ventiltriebskomponenten zu untersuchen. Um Zeit und Kosten zu sparen, wird nach einem Modellprüfsystem verlangt.

Basierend auf einem Rotationstribometer, wurde ein Prüfstand entwickelt, der Untersuchungen unterschiedlicher Kugelgelenksproben, die aus Ventiltriebskomponenten geschnitten werden, innerhalb eines Tages ermöglicht. Der modulare Aufbau des Prüfstandes ermöglicht es, verschiedene Proben, deren Einbauposition, Schmiersystem und Kinematik zu variieren. Ein passendes Testprogramm mit Datenauswertung, basierend auf einem Start-Stopp-Zyklus, wurde entwickelt, um die realen Laufeigenschaften im Motor bestmöglich zu simulieren. Die Ergebnisse mit begleitender optischer Analyse und gravimetrischer Verschleißmessung werden mit Motortests verglichen. Aufgrund der unterschiedlichen Rotationsachse im Tribometer und im Motor, war es erforderlich, Geschwindigkeit und Last anzupassen, um den gleichen feinabrasiven Verschleißmechanismus zu erzielen, der in Motorkomponenten festgestellt wurde. Da Versuche mit ungebrauchtem Motoröl nicht genügend Verschleiß produzieren konnten, um die Ölwirksamkeit zu erproben, wurde eine künstliche Ölalterung durch Beimischung von Abrasivpartikeln oder einem Rußersatz erzielt.

Es konnte gezeigt werden, dass die geometrische Konformität von Kugel und Kugelpfanne einen großen Einfluss auf die Reproduzierbarkeit und den eventuellen Aufbau eines tragenden Ölfilms hat. Versuche mit gebrauchtem Motoröl konnten beweisen, dass es möglich ist, signifikanten Verschleiß an den untersuchten Teilen in moderater Versuchsdauer zu erzeugen. Weiters konnte gezeigt werden, dass, abhängig von deren Konzentration, Abrasivpartikel an den untersuchten Kontakten zwar den Reibungskoeffizienten erhöhen und zum Fressen führen können, aber nicht den feinabrasiven Verschleiß erhöhen. Das Beimischen von Rußersatz dagegen führt zu einer deutlichen Erhöhung des Verschleißes. Laut Literatur ist dies auf eine chemische Interaktion zwischen Ruß und dem Öl-Additiv Zinkdialkyldithio-

phosphat zurückzuführen. Zum Zwecke der Validierung wurden Versuche mit Ölen unterschiedlicher Laufleistungen im Motor durchgeführt. Es konnte gezeigt werden, dass ein Öl mit niedrigem Verschleiß im Motortest, unter Anwendung künstlicher Ölalterung, auch zu niedrigem Verschleiß im Modell führt. Folglich bietet die entwickelte Versuchsmethodik ein gutes Werkzeug zum besseren Verständnis und zur Bewertung von Tribosystemen mit Kugelgelenken.

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List of abbreviations

ACEA	European Automotive Manufacturers Association
AD	Arizona Dust
ASTM	American Society for Testing and Materials
CAD	Computer Aided Design
CB	Carbon Black
CCS	Cold Cranking Simulator
COF	Coefficient of Friction
DC	Direct Current
DIN	German Industrial Standard
DOHC	Double Overhead Camshaft
EDX	Energy Dispersive X-ray Spectroscopy
EP	Extreme Pressure
HFRR	High Frequency Reciprocating Rig
HTHS	High Temperature High Shear
HV	Vickers Hardness
ISO	International Organization for Standardization
MRV	Mini Rotary Viscometer
OHC	Overhead Camshaft
OHV	Overhead Valves
PB	Pivot Ball
PD	Pedestal
PR	Push Rod
RA	Rocker Arm
SAE	Society of Automotive Engineers
SEM	Scanning Electron Microscope
TSV	Tab Separated Values
VI	Viscosity index
ZDDP	Zinc Dialkyldithiophosphate

1 Introduction

Nowadays combustion engines still make an important contribution to the worldwide economic performance. While alternative concepts for passenger transportation are in development, it seems that in some sectors combustion engines are hardly replaceable. Especially in the utility vehicle sector, there is currently no alternative to heavy duty diesel engines.

Due to increasingly strict environmental regulations to meet climate goals and to reduce air pollution, combustion engines must become more efficient and emissions must be minimized. ACEA members (European Automobile Manufacturers' Association) have already significantly reduced CO₂ and pollutant emissions from new heavy-duty vehicles in the last years. In addition, the manufacturers commit to CO₂ reduction targets for the years 2025 and 2030, as proposed by the European Commission in May 2018. In fact, they agreed to reduce CO₂ emissions by 7% by 2025 and even 16% by 2030. According to ACEA members, these goals strike the right balance between being ambitious and realistic. [1]

Optimizations like forced induction, exhaust gas treatment and friction reduction are crucial to achieving these goals. Considering that about 10% of the fuel energy is lost in engine friction, there is big energy-saving potential [2]. For friction reduction engine oils with low viscosity are required. On the one hand, those low-viscosity engine oils provide lower friction losses in the hydrodynamic lubrication regime, but on the other hand they reduce the reliability and increase engine wear.

Environmental regulations also limit certain oil additives, especially the ash forming and phosphorous content must be reduced. Phosphorus is a component of one of the most common engine oil additives - zinc dialkyldithiophosphate (ZDDP), which is a multipurpose additive. It reduces wear, inhibits oxidation, prevents corrosion, and consequently increases the lifespan of the engine [3]. However, modern catalysts do not tolerate high ZDDP contents.

Lower viscosity and reduced phosphorous content lead to wear on engine components, which were uncritical in the past. Particularly at ball/socket-contacts wear has become an important issue now.

Ball/socket-contacts are frequently used in valvetrains. The valvetrain is one of the

highest loaded and most important modules of a combustion engine and controls the gas exchange of the combustion chamber. Minimal geometrical changes due to wear in valvetrain components can lead to efficiency loss or total engine failure in worst case.

So it is necessary to investigate the tribological behavior of ball/socket-contacts under those tough conditions. Since it would not be economically reasonable to do this only by real engine tests, a model-based testing system is required.

In this thesis a test rig and a suitable test routine are developed. The aim of this test rig is to simulate similar conditions and the same wear mechanism as in a real engine. To prove the same wear mechanism, worn surfaces of engine tests and model tests are analyzed and compared.

2 Task

The aim of this thesis is to investigate the tribological behavior of ball/socket-contacts, especially under the tough conditions which occur in a valvetrain of an internal combustion engine. This includes relative motion, load, temperature and lubrication. A schematic illustration of a ball/socket-contact is depicted in figure 2.1. Therefore, a model testing system has to be designed, which is based on a rotational tribometer. The test setup should simulate the conditions in the real-case application as closely as possible.

Figure 2.1: Schematic illustration of a ball/socket-contact

To provide flexibility and in order to use the test rig also for future research projects, it is required to enable different types of lubrication and allow different assemblies with a modular construction. The test rig must fulfill the following requirements:

- Specimens: original engine parts (rocker arm, push rod, pedestal, pivot ball), alternative materials (e.g. bearing materials)
- Positions: fixed bottom-mounted socket / rotating ball, fixed bottom-mounted ball / rotating socket
- Lubrication: drop-feed, pressure-feed, oil bath
- Motion: low rotational speed, start stop in one direction, alternating

Firstly, the main goal is to achieve the same wear mechanism as found in a real engine. Secondly, an appropriate test routine has to be developed to perform reproducible tests. Finally, comparative tests have to be performed to prove that model tests follow the same trends as observed in engine tests. This would allow to use the developed testing system for future tribosystem-screening to find the best materials and lubricants for this application.

3 State of the art

In the following chapter selected fundamentals of tribology, valvetrains, ball/socket-contacts and lubricants are explained.

3.1 Tribology

Tribology is the science and technology of interacting surfaces in relative motion. The main fields of research and application are friction, wear and lubrication. The term tribology is derived from the Greek word *tribos*, which means rubbing. [4]

3.1.1 Tribological system

A tribosystem is an entity with a structure of interacting components in relative motion, in order to perform a technical task. [5]

Figure 3.1: Structure, function and examples of tribosystems [6]

As shown in figure 3.1, many functions are realized by contacting surfaces in relative motion. This leads to friction and wear on the interacting materials, parts and assemblies. Friction and wear are no material properties and cannot be described by simple material characteristics like hardness or modulus of elasticity, for example. Friction and wear are system properties. To evaluate them, it is necessary to analyze and consider all parameters and influencing variables of the whole tribological system. [6]

Structure and interactions

In figure 3.2 a schematic structure of a tribosystem and its interactions is depicted. A tribosystem always consists of two triboelements, a base body (1) and a counter body (2), which contact with each other. Depending on the other components and the influencing parameters, the contact leads to deformation, adhesion, abrasion and tribochemical reactions. In case of many tribosystems there is also an interfacial medium (3) between the triboelements, usually a lubricant like oil. It adsorbs on the surfaces of both triboelements, lubricates and is also able to react with the triboelements. And not to forget, there is always an ambient medium (4) present, which can significantly affect the tribosystem. This is usually air, but can also be any other fluid or pollution. It also adsorbs on both triboelements and reacts with the triboelements or the interfacial medium.

Figure 3.2: Schematic structure and interactions in a tribosystem [7]

Function

According to the system theory, tribosystems can be described as followed [4]:

$$\{X\} + D \rightarrow S = f(A, B, R) \rightarrow \{Y\} + \{Z\} \quad (3.1)$$

$\{X\}$ = input: type of motion (rolling, sliding), $F(t), M(t), T(t), v(t)$

$\{Y\}$ = output: motion, power, information, matter, materials

$\{Z\}$ = loss: energy loss, material loss (wear)

D = disturbances: vibrations, dust

S = structure of the tribosystem

A = elements: base and counter body, intermediate and ambient medium

B = properties of the elements: material, shape, viscosity, etc.

R = interaction: friction condition, wear mechanism, etc.

System boundaries

Tribosystems can be characterized as either open or closed. This is relevant when diagnosing wear problems, especially those concerning lubricants.

- Tribosystems with closed system boundaries are mainly used to transfer motion, forces, energy or signals. Their elements are continuously or intermittent exposed to the tribological stress. Typical examples are gears, clutches, bearings and relays (transfer signals, information). A pump with a recirculating working fluid or a bearing, which is sealed for life, represents also closed tribosystems.
- Tribosystems with open system boundaries are primary matter determined. This means that a permanent material flow occurs in and out of the system. Typical examples are conveying systems like pipelines, screw- or belt conveyors and manufacturing systems. Open tribosystems have the potential to introduce other chemical species or contaminants, which affect the tribosystem.

Some systems have both open and closed characteristics. An internal combustion engine, for example, has a recirculating oil and coolant system, but it has the potential to introduce wear causing particles through air or fuel intakes if filters are not working properly. [6], [8], [9]

Stability

Depending on the tribological load a tribosystem can be stable or unstable. Stability is important for a proper function of the tribosystem and is dependent of its wear state. Exceeding stability limits leads to a shorter lifetime and seizure or a renewed stabilization. Knowledge of the stability limits allows better predictions regarding reliability and lifetime of the tribosystem. [10]

Energy balance

The energy transfer in a tribosystem is always connected with losses. This leads to a reduction of efficiency in all tribological systems. [11], [6]

$$W_0 = W_s + W_e + W_t + W_u \quad (3.2)$$

W_0 = supplied energy [J]

W_s = stored energy in material defects and residual stresses [J]

W_e = acoustic emissions [J]

W_t = energy conversion into heat [J]

W_u = usable energy [J]

Mass balance

The masses of individual components in a tribosystem vary. This is due to the following phenomenons between the components:

- material removal
- material transfer
- chemical reactions

3.1.2 Friction

Friction is the resistance of two contacting bodies against relative motion. It is not a material property, it is a property of the tribological system. [12] Friction is manifested as the force that must be overcome to initiate or sustain motion, and as the energy dissipated during relative motion. [13] Commonly two main types of friction are encountered, dry friction and fluid friction. Dry friction is also called *Coulomb friction* and describes the tangential component of the contact

force when two dry surfaces move or tend to move relatively to each other. Fluid friction describes the tangential component of the contact force when two adjacent layers in a fluid move in different velocities to each other. [14]

Friction mechanisms

Friction mechanisms are locally occurring macroscopic processes at the contacting area. These processes are basically responsible for hindering movement and dissipating energy.

Bowden and Tabor [15] established a fundamental theory to explain the causes of friction. According to their theory, friction is combined of two components.

$$\mu = \mu_a + \mu_p \tag{3.3}$$

$$\mu_a = \text{adhesive component} \quad [-]$$

$$\mu_p = \text{plowing component} \quad [-]$$

The components in equation 3.3 are completely independent of each other. The adhesive component μ_a is dependent of the material pair, lubrication and the real area of contact. The plowing component μ_p is dependent on deformation taking place at the asperity level. [12]

As pictured in figure 3.3, surfaces are never completely smooth. The sliding surfaces contact in certain sites, so that the real contact area is much smaller than the nominal area. These contact points support the whole load, so that the real pressure is much higher than the calculated pressure.

There are four fundamental friction mechanisms of solids, which are also pictured in figure 3.3 and will be basically described in the following. In reality friction mechanisms superpose in a permanent changing intensity, so that it is not possible to characterize the real friction behavior theoretically. Real friction behavior can only be characterized experimentally. [16] [6]

Figure 3.3: Overview of dry friction mechanisms [17]

Adhesion

Adhesion means as much as *sticking on*. When two solids approach each other, they are affected by certain attraction forces, called adhesion forces. This is illustrated in figure 3.4. Those adhesion forces have the same cause as atomic bonds inside the solids. Those are metallic-, covalent-, ionic- or Van-Der-Waals bonds, which lead to a forced closure between the surfaces. Furthermore, clinging of makroscopic roughness peaks leads to form closure, which is also considered as adhesion. These junctions caused on microscopic and macroscopic level must be sheared off for relative movement. This happens for the weakest layer, which can also be different than original separation plane and can lead to material transfer. For destruction of this cold welded junctions a certain force must be applied and energy is dissipated, which will appear as friction. [18] [19]

Figure 3.4: Adhesion [17]

Deformation

When two bodies are contacting and moving relatively, surface deformations take place. Plastic deformation leads to dissipation of energy. The deformation behavior was analyzed by Green and Drescher based on a flow line model for ideal plastic bodies, which is illustrated in figure 3.5. According to this theory, a roughness peak contact AB leads to three different zones of plastic deformed material ABE, BED and BCD. The maximal shear stress in this process is the flow shear stress of the softer material. [6] [20]-[21]

Figure 3.5: Flow line model for deformation [6]

Plowing

When two bodies with different hardness contact with each other, the harder body can penetrate the softer surface. Tangential movement forms a groove and the resistance of the softer material leads to friction. There are two types of plowing, counter body plowing or particle plowing. It is called counter body plowing, when the penetrating body is a roughness peak of the counter body. Particle plowing occurs, when the penetrating body is foreign, a wear particle for example. This is pictured in figure 3.6. [6] [22]

Figure 3.6: Particle plowing [22]

Hysteresis

Contact and relative motion can also lead to elastic deformation, which causes oscillation of the atomic grid. This is pictured in a nano model in figure 3.7. These vibrations are damped, which means that energy is dissipated. [6]

Figure 3.7: Nano model of hysteresis [6]

Coefficient of friction

Referring to figure 3.8, the coefficient of friction is defined in equation 3.4 as the dimensionless ratio of friction force F_R and the normal force F_N . The coefficient of friction is usually symbolized by the Greek letter μ , sometimes as COF or f . μ is not a material property, but a system property and can only be determined experimentally. [4]

Figure 3.8: Schematic model of a body in motion [4]

$$\mu = \frac{F_R}{F_N} \quad (3.4)$$

μ = coefficient of friction [-]

F_R = friction force [N]

F_N = normal force [N]

Two coefficients of friction are distinguished:

$$\mu_s = \text{static coefficient of friction} \quad [-]$$

$$\mu_k = \text{kinetic coefficient of friction} \quad [-]$$

The static coefficient of friction μ_s occurs when the two bodies do not move relatively and corresponds to the tangential force that must be applied to initiate motion. The kinetic coefficient of friction μ_k occurs when relative motion and is sometimes also called dynamic coefficient of friction. The static coefficient of friction is usually higher than the kinetic coefficient of friction ($\mu_s > \mu_k$). This is due to adhesion and the effect of the two bodies sticking together, also called stiction. Once motion is initiated, the static coefficient of friction μ_s is not longer applicable but the kinetic coefficient of friction μ_k is applicable . [4] [12]

Friction regimes

In tribological systems, different forms of contact situations can exist. This mainly depends on the the lubrication conditions. When lubrication is not present it is called *dry friction*. Dry friction means that two solids contact each other without any separating layer between them. Friction coefficients and wear rates are usually high, especially when conventional materials are involved. Lubrication technologies try to avoid this condition. As soon as lubricant is present, three types of friction regimes can be defined: [4]:

- Boundary friction
- Mixed friction
- Fluid film friction

The friction condition depends on the roughness R of the contacting surfaces and the Hersey number H, which is defined as followed in equation 3.5. [24]

$$H = \frac{\eta \cdot \omega}{p} \quad (3.5)$$

$$H = \text{Hersey number} \quad [-]$$

$$\eta = \text{dynamic viscosity of the lubricant} \quad [Pa \cdot s]$$

$$\omega = \text{speed} \quad [s^{-1}]$$

$$p = \text{load} \quad [Pa]$$

Figure 3.9: Friction regimes [23]

Depending on the Hersey number H , the friction coefficient μ has a characteristic graph. This diagram is well known as the stribeck curve, named after Professor Richard Stribeck [25]. The stribeck curve is pictured in figure 3.10 and characterizes different lubrication conditions. On the left side boundary friction occurs, where the friction coefficient and wear are usually highest. Upon increase of the Hersey number mixed friction conditions take place. At a certain point a sufficiently thick lubrication film is formed and the coefficient of friction reaches its minimum. This point is often called release point. From here the next condition begins, which is called fluid friction. Here the surfaces are completely separated by the fluid film, the external load is carried by the lubricant between the surfaces based on hydrodynamic pressure formation. A further increase of the friction coefficient is due to inner friction of the fluid.

Boundary friction

The contacting bodies are covered with a thin adsorption layer of lubricant, but the load is transferred by contacting roughness peaks of the bodies. This is pictured on the left in figure 3.9. Consequently there is no load bearing lubrication film ($h=0$). Adsorption, surface active substances, their chemical reaction products and tribochemical reactions cause boundary lubricant films. [4]

Fluid film friction

In this friction regime, both surfaces are completely separated by a load bearing fluid lubricant film ($h \gg R$, with $R = \text{Roughness}$). This is pictured on the right in figure 3.9. This is caused either hydrostatically or hydrodynamically. The COF

Figure 3.10: Stribeck curve [26]

in this regime is caused by shear stresses in the lubricant fluid and depends on its rheological properties, like viscosity. When the surfaces are separated by a gas, it is called *gas lubrication*. [4]

Mixed friction

As its name suggests, mixed friction is a combination of boundary friction and fluid film friction. The height of the load bearing lubrication film is approximately the height of the roughness peaks ($h \approx R$). This is pictured in the middle in figure 3.9. It has been shown that for roller bearings the formed fluid lubrication film, caused by the viscosity of a oil or even a grease, is not sufficient to ensure the required lifetime of the roller bearing. Therefore it is necessary to choose a lubricant with the right anti-wear and extreme-pressure additives to form tribolayers, which resist the tough conditions of mixed friction. [27] [4]

3.1.3 Wear

Wear is the proceeding loss of material from the surface of a solid body, caused by tribological stress. This means contact and relative motion of a solid, liquid or gaseous counter body. [6]

Wear mechanisms

Wear mechanisms are physical and chemical interactions in the contacting area of a tribological system. These elementary processes lead to a change of material and shape of the contacting bodies. They occur at micro contacts in the contacting area and their contribution to the total wear depends on the structure of the tribological system and the tribological stress. There are four fundamental wear mechanisms, which are pictured in figure 3.11. [6] [28]

Figure 3.11: Schematic images of the four representative wear mechanisms [18]

Adhesive wear

While abrasive and fatigue wear are caused by contact mechanics, that means forces, stresses and deformations, adhesive wear is caused by interactions on a molecular level [29]. Adhesive wear occurs when protecting surface layers on roughness peaks are burst due to tribological stress, especially due to high local pressure. This leads to local boundary surface bonds. [30] These boundary surface bonds, which are also called *cold weldings* when metallic materials are involved, can often have higher mechanical strength than the original materials. When the contacting bodies are then moved relatively, the material breaks at the weakest layer, which can lead to material transfer. Figure 3.12 shows a scanning electron microscope (SEM) photo of adhesive material transfer due to local seizure on a steel/steel sliding pair. This explains while some worn parts gain weight, while the other contact partner loses weight. [6]

Figure 3.12: Adhesive material transfer on a steel/steel sliding pair [6]

Abrasive wear

Abrasion in tribological contacts occurs when the counter body is significantly harder and rougher than the base body or when hard particles are somehow introduced to the contact. These particles are then pushed into the softer material [31]. At relative motion various material separating processes occur and cause abrasive wear in the softer ground body. There are four types of material separating processes, which are pictured in figure 3.13. The predominant material separation process depends on the ductility of the material and the inclination angle of the effecting abrasive material, which can be considered as rake angle. Obtuse angles cause micro plowing and acute angles cause micro-chipping, which leads to higher wear than micro-plowing. Micro-bursting mainly occurs in brittle materials. At certain conditions abrasive particles can also lead to rolling abrasion, which is further described in the following. [32] [6]

Figure 3.13: Material separating processes of abrasive wear [32]

Depending on the interactions between the elements in the tribosystem two different abrasive wear modes can be distinguished: grooving abrasion (two-body abrasion) and rolling abrasion (three-body abrasion), which are pictured in figure 3.14. One approach to distinguish between abrasive wear modes has been established by Adachi K. et al. [33] by creating wear mode maps, illustrated in figure 3.15. It shows the dependance of the severity of the contact S and the hardness

ratio of the contacting triboelements. For rolling abrasion the criteria in equation 3.6 must be fulfilled. This map was created by performing the micro-scale abrasion test, also known as the ball cratering abrasive wear test. Thereby a ball rotates against a specimen in presence of a slurry of fine abrasive particles. As abrasive particles predominantly silicon carbide but also diamond and alumina was used. [33]-[34]

Figure 3.14: Principle of: (a) Grooving abrasion [35], (b) Rolling abrasion [35] Abrasive wear pattern: (c) Grooving abrasion [36], (d) Rolling abrasion [37]

Figure 3.15: Wear mode map created by observations in [33] and also reported in [37], [38] and [39]

$$S = \frac{W}{AvH'} \leq \alpha \left(\frac{H_s}{H_b} \right)^\beta \quad (3.6)$$

with

$$\frac{1}{H'} = \frac{1}{H_b} + \frac{1}{H_s} \quad (3.7)$$

S	= severity of the contact	[–]
W	= applied load	[N]
A	= interaction or wear scar area	[m ²]
v	= volume fraction of abrasive in the slurry	[–]
H_s	= hardness of specimen	[HV]
H_b	= hardness of ball	[HV]
α	= 0.0076	[–]
β	= –0.49	[–]

Fatigue wear

In all tribological systems the contacting surface areas absorb forces, which stress the material, especially with in combination with relative motion of the contacting partners. At fluid film friction this occurs via a load bearing lubrication film. At dry-, boundary- or mixed friction the effecting tangential- and normal forces are partially or fully absorbed by the micro contacts. This strain often occurs periodically and can lead to a damage accumulation and material fatigue. Especially parts with hertzian contacts, like roller bearings, gears or other parts with alternating tribological strains, are affected by this wear mechanism. The superposition of normal- and tangential forces can lead to stress maximums underneath the surface. The material underneath the surface is consequently exposed to alternating multi-axial tensile and compression stresses. As a consequence, cracks are initiated and grow. Depending on material properties the cracks grow till finally a piece of material breaks out and leaves a pit behind. This is called *pitting* and is pictured in figure 3.16. If the crack grows parallel to the surface and the material flakes, it is called *delamination*. [40] [41]

Figure 3.16: Example of fatigue wear [6]

Corrosive wear

Corrosive wear is caused by tribochemical reactions, which are chemical reactions between base body, counter body and the interfacial or ambient medium. These reactions are caused or increased by tribological stress. The tribological stressed surfaces react under relative motion, so that the reaction products are constantly formed and rubbed off again. This leads to an appearance like in figure 3.17. [42]

Figure 3.17: Appearance of corrosive wear [6]

Several factors increase the reactivity of tribochemical interactions [43] [44]:

- Removal of reaction inhibiting top layers
- Faster transport of reactants
- Increase of the active area
- Increase of temperature due to frictional heat
- Surface atoms with free valence electrons due to lattice imperfections, caused by plastic deformation

Tribochemical reactions change the properties of boundary layers of the contacting partners. This results in an increase or decrease of wear. A very important parameter is the humidity, especially on metallic contacts. [6] [45]

Wear measurement

Depending on the geometry and the measurement technology, direct wear values can be described by different parameters. The reciprocal value of wear W is called *wear resistances* $\frac{1}{W}$. [6]

- Wear length (or height) W_L [mm]: one-dimensional change of geometry perpendicular to the contacting surface (linear wear value)
- Wear area W_q [mm²]: two-dimensional change of tribological stressed sections (planimetric wear value)
- Wear volume W_V [mm³]: three-dimensional change of tribological stressed sections (volumetric wear value)
- Wear mass W_m [g]: at constant density direct proportional to wear volume, but mostly easier to measure (gravimetric wear)

Besides the already mentioned direct wear values, there are also indirect wear values. Indirect wear values refer to a reference value and are also called *wear rates*. The most common wear rates are: [6]

- Wear-time-ratio
- Wear-distance-ratio
- Wear-flow-rate-ratio

The global standard reference for wear is the *specific wear rate* k , sometimes also called *wear factor*. It is defined as followed in equation 3.8 and describes a wear rate depending on the tribological stress [46]:

$$k = \frac{W_V}{F_N \cdot s} \quad (3.8)$$

k = specific wear rate	$[mm^3/Nm]$
W_V = wear volume	$[mm^3]$
F_N = normal force	$[N]$
s = sliding distance	$[m]$

3.2 Valvetrain

The function of a valvetrain in an internal combustion engine is to control the gas exchange by opening and closing the valves. It ensures that fresh air or gas-air-mixture enters, and exhaust gases exit the combustion chamber at the right moment. This is crucial for a controlled combustion process. Therefore, energy is needed, which is provided by the crankshaft via chain drive or toothed belt. Consequently, a well designed valvetrain significantly contributes to a high efficiency of the engine. [47]

3.2.1 Valvetrain types

Valvetrains can be categorized by position and amount of camshafts, which is pictured in figure 3.18.

Figure 3.18: Types of valvetrains [48]

OHV

Originally, combustion engines have been designed with one camshaft in the crank case with inlet and exhaust cams. This design is called overhead valves (OHV) and is still in use, especially in big engines with high displacement and cylinders in V-configuration. In OHV valvetrains many transmission parts are necessary to transmit the cam lift to the valve as seen in figure 3.18. They consist of tappet, push rod, rocker arm and rocker arm bearing. OHV valvetrains are inexpensive to produce, but have low stiffness, due to the high amount of transmitting parts. This limits the rotational speed. [2] [47] [48]

OHC

When the camshaft is placed in the cylinder head, above the valves, it is called overhead camshaft (OHC). In this design no tappet nor push rod is needed and the cam lift can be directly transmitted via the rocker arm. The higher stiffness allows higher rotational speeds. [2] [47] [48]

DOHC

When two camshafts are built-in above the valves, it is called double overhead camshaft (DOHC). In this case one camshaft controls the inlet valves and the other controls the exhaust valves. This allows an independent control of inlet- and exhaust times. In the last years OHC and DOHC have become standard for passenger cars. [2] [47] [48]

3.2.2 Valve clearance

To compensate geometric changes of various engine parts, a valvetrain must have a precisely defined range when the valve is closed. Reasons for geometric changes can be temperature fluctuations, the use of materials with different thermal expansion or wear on contacts between cam and valve. [48]

If the valve clearance is too small, the valve opens earlier and closes later. This leads to a reduction of the valve closing time, which can have the following effects [48]:

- Not enough heat can be transferred from the valve disc to the valve seat
- The exhaust valve disc overheats and can break
- The valves do not close properly when the engine is warm
- Exhaust gases can be sucked back into the combustion chamber at the exhaust valve and flames can enter the intake tract through the inlet valve
- Gas and performance losses occur, which leads to higher emissions

If the valve clearance is too big, the valve opens later and closes earlier. This leads to a reduction of the valve opening time and smaller opening cross sections, which can have the following effects [48]:

- The filling ration of the cylinder with air or ignitable mixture reduces, which leads to higher emissions
- Engine torque and performance decreases
- High mechanical stress of the valve
- Acoustic emissions at the valvetrain

The valve clearance can be adjusted mechanically or hydraulically. Both options are pictured in figure 3.19. For engines with mechanical adjustment the valve clearance is adjusted with a screw in certain maintenance intervals. The hydraulic adjustment automatically compensates the valve clearance in a running engine. [48]

Figure 3.19: Mechanical and hydraulic valve clearance adjustment [47]

3.2.3 Kinematics

The arrangement of valvetrain components depends on the type, purpose and related physical values like rotational speed, valve timing and opening cross section. Cams and valves exist in all valvetrains. Tappets, push rods and rocker arms can be present. If rocker arms are used, the kinematic values valve lift h_V , tappet lift s , valve speed v_V , tappet speed v , valve acceleration α_V and tappet acceleration a are linked by simple geometric relations. Therefore the rocker arm ratio is defined in equation 3.9 and shown in figure 3.20. If the valve is directly driven, such as for DOHC in figure 3.18, the kinematic values for valve and tappet are identical and $i = 1$. [49].

$$i = \frac{L_1}{L_2} \quad (3.9)$$

Consequently, for the kinematic values applies:

$$h_V = i \cdot s \quad (3.10)$$

$$v_V = i \cdot v \quad (3.11)$$

$$a_V = i \cdot a \quad (3.12)$$

i = rocker arm ratio	[—]
L_1, L_2 = rocker arm lengths	[mm]
h_V = valve lift	[mm]
s = tappet lift	[mm]
v_V = valve speed	[m/s]
v = tappet speed	[m/s]
a_V = valve acceleration	[m/s ²]
a = tappet acceleration	[m/s ²]

Figure 3.20: Arrangement of valvetrain components in a diesel engine. (1) camshaft; (2) tappet; (3) push rod; (4) rocker arm; (5) valve spring; (6) valve [49]

3.2.4 Forces

In a valvetrain inertia-, spring-, gas-, friction- and elastic deformation forces exist. Considering the safety reserves, friction forces are usually neglected for calculation. Normally, the gas forces are also neglected because the gas forces are relatively small in relation to inertia forces at high rotational speeds. This applies especially for suction engines. The motion of the valve occurs via form closure for acceleration and via force closure for deceleration. The force closure can be interrupted due to oscillation, damaged or too weak springs. This happens when the inertia forces, which are proportional to the square of the engines rotational speed, exceed the spring forces. Consequently, the inertia forces and spring forces are the most important issues when calculating a valvetrain. [49]

Inertia forces

The high acceleration and deceleration in a valvetrain leads to inertia forces, which represent the largest share of the mechanical stress in a valvetrain. Depending on which calculation is needed, the inertia forces can be reduced to either valve or cam side (see figure 3.20). If the valve spring is calculated, the reduced mass on the valve side m_{redV} is needed. If the surface pressure between cam and tappet is calculated, the reduced mass on cam side m_{red} is needed, see the following equations 3.16 - 3.20. [49]

$$m_{redV} = m_V + \frac{m_S}{3} + (m_T + m_{PR}) \cdot \frac{L_2^2}{L_1^2} + \frac{J_R}{L_1^2} \quad (3.16)$$

$$m_{redC} = m_T + m_{PR} + (m_V + \frac{m_S}{3}) \cdot \frac{L_1^2}{L_2^2} + \frac{J_R}{L_2^2} \quad (3.17)$$

m_{redV}	= reduced mass on valve side	[kg]
m_{redC}	= reduced mass on cam side	[kg]
m_V	= mass of valve	[kg]
m_S	= mass of spring	[kg]
m_T	= mass of tappet	[kg]
m_{PR}	= mass of push rod	[kg]

L_1 = length 1 on rocker arm, see figure 3.20	[mm]
L_2 = length 2 on rocker arm, see figure 3.20	[mm]
J_R = moment of inertia of rocker arm	[kg · mm ²]

The following relation exists between m_{redV} and m_{redC} :

$$m_{redC} = i^2 \cdot m_{redV} \quad (3.18)$$

The inertia forces on the valve side F_{mV} and on the cam side F_{mC} are:

$$F_{mV} = m_{redV} \cdot a_V \quad (3.19)$$

$$F_{mC} = m_{redC} \cdot a \quad (3.20)$$

Spring force

As seen in figure 3.22, the spring force is dependent on the cam rotation angle φ and the valve lift h_V . The angles ϕ_1 and ϕ_g are explained in figure 3.21. The total valve spring force has two components, a preload force F_{S0} and a valve-lift-dependent force. The preload force F_{S0} is due to the compression f_0 at assembly. This is summed up in equation 3.21 [49].

Figure 3.22: Spring force diagram [49]

$$F_S = F_{S0} + c \cdot h_V \quad (3.21)$$

F_S	= spring force	[N]
F_{F0}	= preload force	[N]
c	= spring constant	[N/mm]
h_V	= valve lift	[mm]

3.3 Ball/socket-contacts

In general, ball/socket contacts allow free rotation in all directions and prevent translation in almost all directions. If the socket encloses the ball further than the equator, translation even in all directions is prevented and it is usually called a ball joint. Ball/socket-contacts are used in many applications, like prosthetic implants for hip replacements in surgery, track rod ends in automotive steering systems and in valvetrains. Figure 3.23 shows a hydraulic adjuster with a ball contacting the socket in the rocker arm. [50]

Figure 3.23: Ball/socket-contact in a valvetrain [51]

Due to their complex motion and high tribological stress, ball/socket-contacts in valvetrains such as in figure 3.23 tend to wear quicker than other valvetrain components. Wear on those contacts is critical, because it affects the valve clearance and the functionality of the engine. Figure 3.24 shows a ball/socket-contact of a

valvetrain with mild wear on the left and increased wear on the right. (1) and (2) on the left side show smoothing marks in the contacting area of the ball head and in the socket, as it normally occurs during operation. The surfaces are still in good working conditions. (3) and (4) on the right side show a critical degree of highly abrasive wear on the ball head and on the socket. This results in distorted ball head and socket geometries. These parts are in bad working condition and must be replaced. [51]

Figure 3.24: (1)(2) normal wear; (3)(4) increased wear on ball/socket-contacts in a valvetrain [51]

3.3.1 Materials in valvetrain ball/socket-contacts

Such as for most tribological loaded surfaces, materials for ball/socket-contacts should have good sliding properties. This means a low COF, high hardness to prevent wear and a smooth surface. Very important for the suitability in a certain application is also the production characteristics, weldability, formability and corrosion resistance. In the following a few material examples are described. [6]

3.3.2 Hardened steel

Steel is the most important material in industry. Its properties depend on carbon content, alloy elements and microstructure, which can be modified by heat treatment. Two very common examples for valvetrain components are the following steels.

- 100Cr6: It is the commonly used rolling bearing steel and is primary used for the balls. With its 1% carbon content it is very good hardenable and

has a high wear resistance. In most cases the balls are grinded and polished after hardening to ensure a smooth surface and a perfect spheric shape.

- C15: This is a common case hardening steel. It contains no further alloy elements and has a carbon content of 0.15%, which is normally not hardenable. Only carburizing, which means diffusion of carbon at high temperature at the edge layer, makes it hardenable at the edge layer. This leads to a ductile core and an extremely hard edge layer with high wear resistance. C15 is also good forgeable, what allows to forge the socket and case harden it afterwards.

3.3.3 Sinter and casting materials

The geometrical form of the socket is very hard to produce. This is why the socket is often sintered or casted around the ball. Common examples therefore are [52]:

- GJL: Cast iron with lamellar graphite is easy to machine and has good sliding properties due to its graphite lamellae. Furthermore it has good damping characteristics. [53]
- Al-Zn-Si3: A high-strength aluminum alloy with good castability. It is primary used for high-pressure die-casting of sockets for ball joints, where the socket encloses the ball further than the equator. The socket is casted around the ball. This ensures a even contact of ball and socket by exactly copying the shape of the ball. [52]
- Sintered steel: It only contains carbon and copper as alloy elements. Sinter materials are classified into porosity classes A to D. A means highest and D means lowest porosity. Commonly sinter class B is used for ball/socket-contacts. [54]

3.4 Lubricants

The purpose of lubricants is to reduce friction and wear in tribological systems. They have two operating principles: a physical and a chemical effect. The physical effect is forms a bearing hydrodynamic fluid film, which separates the contacting bodies. This happens with respect to the stribeck-curve (see figure 3.10). The chemical effect is to modify boundary layers and form lubricating and protecting surfaces. Lubricants exist in various aggregate conditions as fluid oils, grease or

solid lubricants. Rarely, even water or gas is used. In technical contacts, especially in ball socket contacts and in valvetrains primary engine oils are used, which are described in the following. [6]

3.4.1 Engine Oils

Engine oils consist of a base oil and additives. Base oils, which are mostly a hydrocarbon compound, can be categorized by their origin [6], [55]:

- Mineral oils are obtained from petroleum and partly from coal. They mainly consist of paraffins, naphthenes and aromatics and are of highest importance for technology.
- Synthetic oils are very expensive and are used for extreme applications where mineral oils are not sufficient enough. They are produced by cracking, oligomerisation, polymerisation and hydrogenation. Commonly used synthetic oils are poly-alpha-olefines and silicone oils.
- Animal and plant oils are used when the lubrication oil could enter the environment.

3.4.2 Viscosity

The viscosity is a measure of the inner friction of a fluid and describes its flowability. In the model in figure 3.25 a force F leads to a shear stress τ_x in an even fluid layer with a thickness of dy . The shear stress τ_x is the ratio of the force F an the area A . This leads to a shift dv_x and a shear rate D , which is defined in equation 3.22. The resistance, which the fluid puts up against this shear rate D , is called dynamic viscosity η and is defined in equation 3.23. The unit of the dynamic viscosity η is $1 \text{ Pa} \cdot \text{s}$ (=10 Poise). [6] [56]

$$D = \frac{dv_x}{dy} \quad (3.22)$$

D = shear rate	[–]
dv_x = shift of fluid layer	[mm/s]
dy = thickness of fluid layer	[mm]

$$\eta = \frac{\tau_x}{D} \quad (3.23)$$

η = dynamic viscosity [Pa · s = 10Poise]

τ_x = shear stress [Pa]

Figure 3.25: Shearing of a fluid layer [6]

The ratio between dynamic viscosity η and density ρ is called kinematic viscosity ν , which is defined in equation 3.24. [6] [56]

$$\nu = \frac{\eta}{\rho} \quad (3.24)$$

ν = kinematic viscosity [m²/s = 10⁴Stokes]

ρ = density [kg/m³]

In DIN 51519 industrial lubricants are classified into groups ISO-VG 2 to ISO-VG 1500, whereby the number refers to the kinematic viscosity ν at 40°C in mm²/s [57]. The viscosity depends on various parameters [6] [56]:

- temperature T
- pressure p
- time t
- (shear rate D)

If the viscosity is independent of the shear rate D , it is called a Newtonian-fluid. Mineral oils and most synthetic oils are Newtonian-fluids. Fluids with a viscosity, which is dependent of the shear rate D , are called Non-Newtonian-fluids. The viscosity of lubricant oils decreases with increasing temperature. Consequently, it is important to record the temperature for every viscosity measurement. The temperature dependance can be described with the following approximation formulas 3.25 and 3.26 (Ubbelohde-Walter). [6] [56]

$$\eta = A \cdot e^{\frac{B}{T+C}} \quad (3.25)$$

$$\lg(\lg(\nu + c)) = K - m \cdot \lg(T) \quad (3.26)$$

- $A, B, C, c, K =$ constants [–]
 $T =$ temperature in Kelvin [K]
 $m =$ gradient of the curve in corresponding $\eta - T$ -diagrams [–]

Viscosity index (VI)

To classify the viscosity, the viscosity index VI was introduced in 1928 with a scale from 0 to 100, where VI=0 is a pure naphtenic oil and VI=100 is a paraffinic reference oil [58]. Figure 3.26 shows the kinematic viscosity ν as a function of temperature in a double logarithmic plot. Due to better refining processes and synthetic oils, VI=100 can be exceeded today.

Figure 3.26: Schematic $\nu - T$ behavior of lubricant oils with different VI

3.4.3 SAE-classification

Engine oils have been classified by their viscosity by the Society of Automotive Engineers (SAE) in cooperation with the American Society for Testing and Materials (ASTM). This classification has also been included in DIN 51511 and is listed in table 3.1. According to table 3.1, there are two types of viscosity classes. The class with a suffix W (winter) has upper limits for cold cranking and pumping viscosity and lower limits for kinematic viscosity at 100°C. The class without a suffix W has lower and upper limits for the kinematic viscosity at 100°C and a minimum high temperature (150°C) high shear rate viscosity. With long chain polymers it is possible to create multigrade oils like 5W-30 or 10W-40 (figure 3.27) to ensure a summer and winter operation. These long chain polymers form a dense ball at low temperatures, open at high temperatures and entangle oneself, which leads to an increase of viscosity. [6] [56] [59]

Grade	Cold cranking, CCS	Cold pumping, MRV	Kinematic viscosity, 100°C		HTHS, 150°C
Unit	cP at T°C	cP at T°C	cSt	cSt	cP
	max.	max.	min.	max.	min.
0W	6200 at -35	60000 at -40	3.8	-	-
5W	6600 at -30	60000 at -35	3.8	-	-
10W	7000 at -25	60000 at -30	4.1	-	-
15W	7000 at -20	60000 at -25	5.6	-	-
20W	9500 at -15	60000 at -20	5.6	-	-
25W	13000 at -10	60000 at -15	9.3	-	-
20	-	-	5.6	<9.3	2.6
30	-	-	9.3	<12.5	2.9
40	-	-	12.5	<16.3	2.9
					(0W-40, 5W-40, 10W-40)
40	-	-	12.5	<16.3	3.7
					(15-40, 20W-40, 25W-40, 40)

Table 3.1: SAE viscosity classes for engine oils [60], dynamic viscosity η in centipoise [$1cP = 10^{-3}Pa \cdot s$], kinematic viscosity ν in centistokes [$1cSt = 10^{-6} \frac{m^2}{s}$], CCS = Cold Cranking Simulator, MRV = Mini Rotary Viscometer, HTHS = High Temperature High Shear

Figure 3.27: Schematic $\nu - T$ behavior of multigrade oil 10W-40

3.4.4 HTHS

HTHS stands for high temperature and high shear rate. It is a viscosity measured at a temperature of 150°C and a shear rate of 10^{-6} , which corresponds to the maximum load in internal combustion engines. In the international viscosity classification SAE J300 minimum allowance values for the HTHS viscosity are listed. [61].

3.4.5 Additives

Base oils, which are mineral, synthetic or vegetable oils, do not always meet the demands of modern high performance lubricants. Therefore base oils are mixed with additives in order to enhance or modify the properties of the lubricant oil. Additives are synthetic chemical substances and can improve existing properties, prevent unwanted effects or introduce new properties to the base oil. Individual additives are added in small amounts of about 0.1-0.5% and normally make up a total of 5-15% of the total lubricant mix. [14] [12] [62]

Additives are classified by their effect and can be classified into three main categories [63]:

- Additives that influence the physical properties of the base oil
- Additives that influence the chemical properties of the base oil
- Additives that influence the metal surfaces of the contacting bodies by modifying their tribological properties

There are many different additives, which differ in their purposes. Specific purposes of lubricant additives are [64] [63]:

- Reduce friction (friction modifier)
- Reduce wear (anti wear)
- Withstand extreme pressure (EP)
- Reduce oxidizability
- Minimize corrosion
- Control contamination by reaction products like wear particles and other debris (dispersants)
- Control the pH-value by neutralizing acids (detergents)
- Reduce excessive decrease of viscosity at high temperatures (VI-improver)
- Decrease the pour point
- Inhibit foam generation

3.4.6 ZDDP

Zinc dialkyldithiophosphate is one of the most common additives in engine oils. It is a multipurpose additive because it acts as an antioxidant, corrosion inhibitor, extreme pressure (EP) and anti wear agent. ZDDP works as a wear protection by forming glassy films on the contacting surfaces. Those films are transparent, contain zinc, phosphorus, oxygen and sulfur and tend to form mounds. This is illustrated in figure 3.28. As perfect as ZDDP may seem, environmental regulations force oil manufacturers to reduce the ZDDP content in modern engine oils due to the toxicity of phosphorus, ash forming and the incompatibility with modern catalysts. This leads to wear on parts, which have not been a problem before. [65] [66]

Figure 3.28: Schematic structure of ZDDP pads and composition [66]

Studies have shown that the anti-wear effect of ZDDP is due to its ability to form a phosphate film and the EP-effect results from forming iron sulphide [67] [68]. Figure 3.29 shows the build up of a solid-like film on a ZDDP-lubricated part at 100°C and its corresponding film thickness over the rubbing time [69].

Figure 3.29: (a) Sequence of interference images showing tribofilm formation by ZDDP on a steel ball, (b) Mean film thickness of ZDDP tribofilm over time [69]

3.4.7 Abrasive particles in engine oils

As already described in section 3.1.3 abrasive wear is caused by hard particles sliding on a softer surface and detaching material, which can occur in a rolling or a grooving wear mode. Abrasive wear classically occurs at parts transporting slurry like pumps or pipelines. But it can also occur at any circulating lubrication systems like in a combustion engine. When any lubricated parts in the system wear, the circulating lubricant is contaminated by abrasive particles, which can cause wear on other parts in the system. [70]

3.4.8 Soot

Soot is an unwanted by-product of the combustion process. Under ideal conditions the combustion of hydrocarbons (fuel) mainly leads to carbon dioxide and water. Ideal conditions are characterized by the stoichiometric composition of the combustion mixture, when enough oxygen is locally present to completely

convert the fuel according to the following chemical equation 3.27. In this case a maximum of heat is released and a maximum of chemical energy is available for mechanical work. In internal combustion engines or turbines the conditions locally differ from ideality, which means sufficient oxygen is not provided for a complete combustion. This leads to an incomplete combustion, where besides water and carbon dioxide, other by-products like carbon monoxide, hydrogen, hydrocarbons and soot are formed. Soot is partially burnt fuel which forms a heterocyclic hydrocarbon particle. Most of the soot escapes with the exhaust gases but a part of it impinges on the cylinder wall where it is scraped into the oil sump by the cylinder rings. It is mixed with the oil in the oil sump and circulates through the engine. In the oil pump, which is usually a gear pump, it is grounded into extremely fine particles and then kept in suspension by lubricant dispresants. [71] [72]

Recent studies have shown that soot particles abrade ZDDP films as rapidly as they form, which leads to a high rate of corrosive-abrasive wear. The main evidence for this statement is that when both ZDDP and soot, as soot substitute called carbon black are present in a lubricant, much higher wear occurs than when either ZDDP or carbon black is absent [73]. Booth et al. [74] studied the additive interactions with soot and observed that oil blends containing ZDDP and carbon black lead to high wear, which he ascribed due to immature anti-wear film formation. Olomolehin et al. [75] found out that when carbon black is added to an oil containing ZDDP, this combination leads to even more wear than when no ZDDP was present. This means ZDDP becomes pro-wear in this case. An adhesive corrosive-abrasive mechanism was suggested, in which the carbon black removes the initial iron sulphide and phosphate antiwear film as quickly as it forms. This leads to a rapid loss of ferrous compounds and high wear. Salehi et al. [76] have also shown a similar wear mechanism for carbon black in formulated engine oil. [73] [77]

As real engine soot is extremely difficult to extract and may be contaminated by additives depending on the used lubricant and fuel, a soot surrogate is commonly used for wear studies. Therefore, furnace or channel carbon black is used. Depending on engine conditions soot may also vary in degree of graphitization and particle size but it has been suggested that some carbon blacks are similar in composition, size and morphology to engine soot. In [75] and [73] the furnace carbon black Cabot Vulcan XC72R was used for wear studies as beeing quite

similar to real engine soot. Furthermore, it forms similar secondary particles as shown in figure 3.30. This makes it a realistic soot surrogate in morphological terms. [74] [73]

Figure 3.30: (a) Engine soot extracted from used diesel engine oil, (b) Furnace carbon black Cabot Vulcan XC72R, (c) Soot collected from cylinder walls of diesel engine [73]

In [73] the effect of steel hardness on soot wear was studied by rubbing steel discs of various hardness against a hard steel ball in a High Frequency Reciprocating Rig (HFRR). It was found out that when hard discs are used, the wear inducing interaction of ZDDP and carbon black is especially high. In this case at least twenty times more wear occurs as when one of these components is absent. It is suggested that high local pressures and thus high shear stresses between two very hard surfaces support the ZDDP reaction, which accelerates the corrosive-abrasive wear mechanism of ZDDP and carbon black.

3.4.9 Lubrication systems

A lubrication system describes how the lubricant is conveyed to the contacting area. It is an important factor in terms of cooling, particle and debris transfer and accessibility to the contacting area.

Drop lubrication

When the oil is dropped down on the contacting area it is called drop lubrication. If the oil really reaches the intended area depends on the geometry and can not be ensured. Due to the oil supply at atmospheric pressure a proper particle and debris transport can not be ensured. Drop lubrication is a very simple and inexpensive lubrication system and is often used for systems with marginal lubrication. [78]

Oil bath and splash lubrication

At oil bath lubrication the contacting area is fully submerged in oil. This ensures an appropriate access of the oil to the contacting area. Furthermore the heat resulting from friction can be transported away from the contact. A heat exchange between the the friction contact and the whole oil bath occurs. This system is suitable to keep the contact temperature as cool as possible. If a moving or rotating part is only partly submerged into the oil bath and the lubricant is conveyed to the contacting area due to the motion of the part, it is called *splash lubrication*. [78]

Pressure lubrication

The pressure lubrication with pumps is the safest and most efficient lubrication system for highly loaded bearings and tribological contacts. The lubricant is conveyed in a closed circuit by a pump with a certain system pressure. The oil is then applied with pressure to the contacting area. Depending on the flow rate, this ensures a good heat and particle transfer. The drained oil is collected and supplies the pump again. [78]

4 Research strategy

Figure 4.1: Schematic illustration of the research strategy.

Photo sources: oil pour [79], sinter powder [80], steel round bar [81], microscope [82], scale [83]

In order to meet the task described in chapter 2, a combined research strategy was developed, which is illustrated in figure 4.1. In the first phase engine components were analyzed to understand the real case application. An optical analysis with a light microscope was performed on selected engine components to investigate the wear mechanism. These selected engine components were running in engine tests for several days. Depending on the oil used in the engine tests, these parts show different wear states.

This was followed by developing a test rig with a modular structure, which allows to vary specimens, lubrication and tribological load. The specimens were all cut out from engine parts to ensure same material and shape properties. Experimental tests were performed in order to simulate the real case application. These tests were accompanied by optical analysis and gravimetric wear measurements. The results were compared with engine test results.

The first goal in model testing was to match the same abrasive wear mechanism as in engine tests. Secondly, a test routine was developed to ensure reproducibility and cause significant wear within one day. Finally, tests with different oils were performed to check if the model tests show the same trends as engine tests.

Same trends in model and engine tests will allow to create a system ranking, where comparative tests with different oils or materials will be performed. This will be a good tool to determine the best suitable lubricants or materials for this application.

5 Analysis of engine parts

In this chapter selected engine parts are analyzed. An overview of the mechanics and lubrication of the investigated valvetrain is given. Furthermore, the new and used condition of its ball/socket-contacts is described.

5.1 Mechanics

Figure 5.2 gives an overview about the valvetrain parts of interest including the various ball/socket-contacts.

Figure 5.1: Overview and mechanics of investigated valvetrain parts

As seen in figure 5.1, the motion from the cam is transferred via a cam follower to the hydraulic adjuster assy, which is supposed to compensate the valve clearance. The push rod connects the hydraulic adjuster assy with the rocker arm and is pivoted with ball/socket-contacts on both ends. The contact between push rod and rocker arm is pressure lubricated through the push rod. The rocker arm transfers the motion from the push rod to the valve with a certain rocker arm ratio $i = 1.5$ and the spring ensures a resetting of the valve into its closing position. The rocker arm is pivoted via the pivot ball to the pedestal, which is mounted to the cylinder head. The ball/socket-contact between rocker arm, pivot ball and pedestal is drop lubricated from the oil gallery above. Four of the just described assemblies are mounted to one pedestal and control one valve each. Every cylinder has two inlet and two exhaust valves.

Wear measurements of real engine tests have shown that the following contacts are most critical for the engine parts of interest. These are pictured in figure 5.2.

- Rocker arm against push rod
- Rocker arm against pivot ball
- Pivot ball against pedestal

Figure 5.2: Critical contacts in valvetrain system of interest

Rocker Arm

The rocker arm is made of C15 steel. It is cut out of sheet metal with a thickness of 4.75mm. Thereafter the flattening for the valve and the sockets for push rod and pivot ball are forged. After all it is case hardened to reach a hardness of 700-800 HV.

Push Rod

The push rod itself is made of a weldable steel pipe with an inner diameter of 3mm and an outer diameter of 8mm. On one end a ball and on the other end a socket is attached by friction welding. The ball is made of 50CrMo4, which is a heat treatable steel. After hardening the ball reaches a surface hardness of 560HV.

Pivot Ball

The pivot ball is a 3/8 inch (9.525mm) steel ball, which is made of 100Cr6. It is grinded and has a hardness of 900 HV.

Pedestal

The pedestal is sintered of a powder metallurgy blend and has a surface hardness of 460 HV.

5.2 New condition

In the following figure 5.3 surfaces of the investigated engine parts are pictured in a new condition. All pictures are made with a *Keyence VHX-5000* light microscope with an optical zoom of 1000x.

Figure 5.3: New condition of investigated engine parts of interest

The surface of the rocker arm socket (figure 5.3a) appears dark and rough, which is due to the case hardening process. The surface of the push rod ball (figure 5.3b) is smooth and shows dark spots, which are precipitations. The surface of the pivot ball (figure 5.3c) is also smooth and shows machining grooves, which is due to the grinding process. The surface of the pedestal (figure 5.3d) is rough and shows dark structures, which are pores due to the sintering process.

5.3 Used condition

In the following section surfaces of worn engine parts are pictured. They are from engine tests with a run time of several days at a constant engine speed. Each engine test was performed with a different oil. One with a good reference oil (in the following referred as "good oil") and one with a poor reference oil (in the following referred as "poor oil"). All pictures are made with a *Keyence VHX-5000* light microscope with a zoom of 1000x.

Push Rod Ball

The push rod has two contacts. The push rod socket is contacting the hydraulic adjuster assy and the push rod ball contacts the rocker arm. The focus is on the push rod ball / rocker arm contact because it is more critical. Figure 5.4 shows the push rod ball contacting the rocker arm. Remarkable are the grooves due to abrasive wear with both oils. The grooves at the good oil test 5.4a are slightly wider. Furthermore, small blue and brown discolorations can be seen with both oils, which could be ZDDP-pads.

Figure 5.4: Used push rod ball surfaces after engine tests with different oils

Rocker Arm

The rocker arm has two contacting sockets. One socket contacts the pivot ball, the other one contacts the push rod ball. Figure 5.5 refers to the contact rocker arm / push rod ball. Figure 5.6 refers to the contact rocker arm / pivot ball. Remarkable is that all of these extremely hard surfaces of the rocker arm are hardly worn. The surfaces seem to be smoother (especially 5.6a) than in new condition in figure 5.3a. The brighter appearance than in new condition is due to light effects in the microscope.

(a) Good oil

(b) Poor oil

Figure 5.5: Used rocker arm socket surfaces contacting push rod ball after engine tests with different oils

(a) Good oil

(b) Poor oil

Figure 5.6: Used rocker arm socket surfaces contacting pivot ball after engine tests with different oils

Pivot Ball

Figure 5.7 shows the surfaces of pivot balls after engine tests with different oils. The pivot ball with poor oil has significantly more wear than with good oil. Strong abrasive wear is seen with poor oil. With good oil the surface looks completely different without abrasive wear grooves but with bright spots. It is assumed that these bright spots are due to breakouts.

Figure 5.7: Used pivot ball surfaces after engine tests with different oils

Pedestal

Figure 5.8 shows the surfaces of pedestal sockets after engine tests with different oils. The surfaces show high abrasive wear with both oils. It is assumed that the dark spots in 5.8b are pores.

Figure 5.8: Used pedestal socket surfaces after engine tests with different oils

6 Experimental methodology

In the following chapter the methodology development is described. Firstly, the specimens and their manufacturing process are discussed. Secondly, the test rig, which is based on a rotary tribometer, and the designed setups for the different specimens are explained. Finally, a first design of the test program and its measured quantities are presented.

6.1 Design considerations

The test rig adapters for the critical contacts mentioned in section 5.1 and pictured in figure 5.2 were designed by using the CAD-software CATIA. The specific designs are described in the the subsections 6.3.1 - 6.3.3. The challenge of the designs was to be as flexible as possible with a minimum of parts to perform tests for the contacts, not only in original configuration, but also in various positions, lubrication systems and motion. In this regard it has been a crucial demand to vary the combination of specimens. In total there are 4 specimen types (rocker arm, push rod, pivot ball, pedestal), 3 possible lubrication systems (drop-feed, pressure-feed, oil bath) and 2 assembly options each (regular, upside down). This results in 24 possible combinations, which shall be able to test.

Another challenge was to ensure that the upper and lower specimens are collinear because even a minimal axial offset leads to wobbling, which leads to higher local tribological stress and falsified test results.

To prevent corrosion between the heated oil and the mechanical parts, all parts are made of stainless steel 1.4305 (X8CrNiS 18-9). It is an austenitic chromium-nickel steel with a high chemical resistance and is due to its added sulfur well suitable for machining. To be flexible in terms of the testing machine and for future research projects, all the adapters are designed to fit on both available rotational tribometers, the TE92 and the TE92HS.

6.2 Specimens

All specimens used in this thesis are cut out of real engine parts to ensure a close to component testing. Therefore original manufactured valvetrain units are carefully disassembled, as seen in figure 6.1. Each unit is for one cylinder and consists of one pedestal, four pivot balls and four rocker arms to control the two inlet and two exhaust valves. To reach the valves on the cylinder, which all have a different position relative to the pedestal, the rocker arms have different shapes and are consistently numbered. The push rods are delivered separately. The challenge was to bring the specimens into a suitable form for the test setup without changing the material properties.

Figure 6.1: Disassembly of original manufactured valvetrain unit

6.2.1 Rocker arm

Each rocker arm has two sockets, as seen in figure 6.2. The external socket contacts the push rod and the internal socket contacts the pivot ball, which contacts the pedestal on the other side. The internal sockets are easier to mount on an adapter, so it is preferred to use the inner sockets for specimen manufacturing.

Figure 6.2: Rocker arm (position 1) before cutting out the part with the internal socket

To prove that there is no difference between internal and external sockets all sockets in a set are 3D-measured with focus variation by a computer controlled light microscope from *Keyence VHX-5000*, which creates a picture of the surface topography as seen in figure 6.3 upper left. In this topography section planes can be created and the resulting cross section can be measured (see figure 6.3). Thereby it was found that there was another small socket at the bottom of the actual socket, which operates as oil reservoir when lubricated. The curvature radius of the actual socket and the distance from its center to the bottom of the reservoir is measured, as pictured in figure 6.3.

Figure 6.3: Measurement of a rocker arm socket (external socket)

The measurement results of external and internal sockets of a selected set are listed in table 6.1. It was found that the depth of the reservoir in the internal sockets spreads wider as in the external sockets but the average only differs 2 μm . The spread of the curvature radius of the internal sockets is 100 μm , the curvature radius of the external sockets only spreads 21 μm . Despite the different spreads, the difference between the averages is only 6 μm . It is clearly shown, that the spread of the same sockets is much bigger than the differences of the averages. This means that the external socket can be substituted by the internal socket.

Rocker arm	Internal socket		External socket	
	Radius [μm]	Reservoir [μm]	Radius [μm]	Reservoir [μm]
N1	4902	758	4903	761
N2	4859	801	4913	751
N3	4959	701	4902	762
N4	4898	762	4923	741
Average	4905	756	4910	754
Spread	100	100	21	21

Table 6.1: Measurement of curvature radius and distance from its center to reservoir bottom in internal and external sockets of rocker arms in a set

In figure 6.4 the finished machined rocker arm specimen is pictured. The blind hole right of the socket is to measure the contact temperature by inserting the tip of a 1.5 mm thermoelement.

Figure 6.4: Finished machined rocker arm specimen

6.2.2 Pedestal

In the engine, the pedestal is mounted on the cylinder head by three mounting supports, which are pictured in 6.5. These mounting supports are irrelevant for testing and have been cut away to ensure that the pedestal fits into the test setup. Because the pedestal is too hard for conventional saws, this is done by a cutting disk. To prevent the pedestal from heating and eventual structural changes, it is water cooled while cutting.

Figure 6.5: Pedestal with mounting supports

In order to fit into the pot, the pedestal has to be cut in pieces. Each pedestal has four sockets to hold a pivot ball and operate as bearing for the four rocker arms. The goal was to use every socket for testing. As the tested socket has to be collinear with the axis of the rotating shaft, it has to be centered by a centering pin. Therefore, a through bore is drilled in the middle of each socket (see figure 6.6). To ensure that this bore does not form an artificial oil reservoir at the bottom of the socket when lubricated, the centering pin has the exact length to fill up the bore to the socket surface. Once centered, the pedestal piece is mounted with a screw between the two sockets on the pedestal adapter. The mounting screw is exactly in the middle of two sockets, which allows to test the other socket on a pedestal piece by offsetting the piece and centering the other socket.

Figure 6.6: Modeling procedure of pedestal specimen

To correctly place the cuts and the bore for the mounting screw and to ensure that everything matches with the whole test setup, a CAD-model with a detailed shape is required (see figure 6.6). Therefore a picture of the pedestal is loaded into CATIA as surface texture. With the picture as template on the sketching plane, the contour is drawn with splines. To ensure the right sizes, reference measurements of the socket diameters and the slits are made. The whole contour is then scaled to match these reference measurements. Then the sketch is extruded to a solid and the sockets and bores are designed. Finally, the cuts are placed and the pedestal pieces are built into the CAD model of the test setup to check the matching.

Due to the complex shape of the pedestal the precise positions of the bores for the centering pin and the mounting screw can only be defined by coordinates. This allows to manufacture the specimen precisely on a milling machine with XYZ-coordinate system. As reference lines the connection line between two sockets and an orthogonal line through one of those is used. This is pictured in figure 6.7.

Figure 6.7: XY-coordinate measurement of the pedestal

In figure 6.8 the finished machined pedestal specimen is pictured. This picture shows the other half of the pedestal as pictured in the test setup in figure 6.6.

Figure 6.8: Finished machined pedestal specimen

6.2.3 Pivot ball

The pivot ball is a standardized roller bearing steel ball and does not require any further preparation.

6.2.4 Push rod

The push rod is cut to a length that only the push rod ball reaches out of the push rod clamp. Due to its hardness it is also cut by a cutting disc. To prevent it from heating and thus structural changes, it is water cooled while cutting. In figure 6.9 the finished machined push rod specimen is pictured. In the notch between ball and rod the 0.2 mm thermoelement loop is encircles the specimen to measure the contact temperature. The original manufactured bore through the push rod ball ensures the pressure lubrication.

Figure 6.9: Finished machined push rod specimen

6.3 Tribometer TE92

All tests are performed on the microprocessor controlled rotary tribometer TE92 from *Plint Tribology*. The TE92 is a versatile test machine with collinear rotating and loading axes and an open test platform for research and development work on materials and lubricants. [84]

The operating principle of a rotary tribometer, as seen in figure 6.10, is to apply a axial load while rotating around the same axis. In this case it is the vertical axis. The axial load is applied by a pneumatic air bellows beneath the traverse

and measured by a load cell. The expansion of the pneumatic air bellows pushes up the traverse, which is guided by two guide columns of polished stainless steel. The rotation is caused by a 2.2 kW DC motor, which drives the rotating shaft via a toothed belt. One specimen is mounted to the rotating shaft by using different specimen holders. The counter body or second specimen is mounted on the fixed pivot mounted platform on the traverse. When a lubricant is present, this is realized by an oil pot. In this case a optional splash guard can be lowered from the rotating shaft over the pot. The platform can be heated by built in cylindrical heating elements, which operate as electric resistance heaters. The platform is mounted via an axial roller bearing to the traverse to allow a measurement of the friction torque. A lever arm is attached to the platform and pushes with a ball against the load cell, which is height adjustable to fit different test setups. The load cell measures a force orthogonal to the rotating motion in a constant orthogonal distance. With this force the friction force and the COF can be calculated. For security reasons the whole machine is cased in a housing and the possibly appearing vapors from heated lubricants are sucked away by an air extraction.

Figure 6.10: Rotary tribometer TE92

6.3.1 Test setup rocker arm / push rod

The contact situation between rocker arm and push rod ball specimen is pictured in figure 6.11. The push rod is fixed and the rocker arm rotates. The contact is pressure lubricated from below through a bore in the push rod, like in reality. For a better inside view the corresponding design is illustrated in figure 6.12 as a section view of the CAD-model and described in the following. In addition, a detailed view of the mounted specimen is illustrated in 6.13.

Figure 6.11: Contacting specimens: rocker arm against push rod

Figure 6.12: CAD design of test setup rocker arm / push rod (section view)

Figure 6.13: Mounted specimens: rocker arm / push rod (3D view)

The pot is fix mounted on the platform with a centering shaft shoulder and is secured against rotation by a pin on the outer edge. The rocker arm adapter is attached by 3 screws to the pot and also centered by a shaft shoulder. On the rocker arm adapter the push rod clamp is mounted by 2 screws. The push rod clamp is slotted and has a bore in the middle, which is slightly bigger in diameter than the push rod. By tightening a clamping screw, the slit and the bore become narrower and the push rod is clamped. This is illustrated in figure 6.13. To ensure the correct position of the push rod, the lower end fits into a center bore in the push rod adapter.

In reality this contact is pressure lubricated through a bore in the push rod. To ensure this in the test setup thin bores in the pot and the push rod adapter lead the oil, which comes from a hose pump, to the push rod and the contact. To minimize leakage a sealing ring between the centering shaft of the pot and push rod adapter is placed. When the oil is squeezed out of the contact it drips down and gathers in the pot, where it is sucked away by the suction hose and supplies the hose pump again. When an oil bath lubrication is needed, the pot is simply filled up with oil and the screwable hose connectors are replaced by sealing screws.

The rocker arm is mounted on a rocker arm holder by two horizontal screws (see figure 6.12 and 6.13). The long centering pin has two tasks. One is to ensure a collinear mounting relative to the rotating shaft. The second task is to plug the bore through the center of the rocker arm to ensure that the oil is squeezed into the contact and the oil reservoir is not artificially enlarged. When a pressure lubrication through the rocker arm is needed, the rocker arm can be placed at the bottom and can be fed by the bores through the pot and the rocker arm adapter. In this case a short centering pin is built in, which only ensures the collinear position but keeps the way free for the oil flow.

Between the holders of the upper specimen, in this case the rocker arm, and the rotating shaft is always a shaft adapter. On the bottom side the shaft adapter centers the rocker arm holders by a shaft shoulder and fixes it by 3 screws. On the top side

it contacts a press fitted ball in the rotating shaft and is secured against rotation by 3 screw bolts from the shaft flange. The ball between shaft adapter and shaft and the slit between flange and shaft adapter can compensate a small collinear offset between the two specimens. The manufactured test setup is pictured in figure 6.14.

Figure 6.14: Test setup rocker arm / push rod

As seen in figure 6.14, the oil bath temperature and the contact temperature can be measured. The oil bath temperature is measured by a thermoelement with 1.5 mm diameter, which passes the pot wall through a bore and is bend inside the pot to fit into a blind hole in the push rod adapter. This is necessary to ensure that the tip of the thermoelement contacts a solid. Otherwise the temperature regulation would fluctuate too much due to convection effects of the heated oil, because the temperature is only measured on the tip of the thermoelement. The thermoelement is fixed by a set screw from above through the pot wall.

The contact temperature is measured by a 0.2 mm thermoelement, which is split up into its two measuring wires and welded together at the tip to form a loop. The temperature is only measured at the tip, where the wires are welded together. The loop with the weld spot in the middle is mounted on the push rod so that the loop encircles the push rod in the groove between push rod ball and rod. This ensures that the thermoelement is always mounted on the same position and the contact temperature is always measured in the same distance from the actual contact. To ensure that the loop and the weld spot always contact the push rod, the thermoelement must be kept under light pull. This occurs by peeling the

outer coating of the thermoelement and only pushing the two wires with their thin inner coating through the pot hole. The peeled outer coating does not fit through the hole in the pot wall. So it operates like a compression spring and keeps the loop inside the pot under a light pull.

The oil feed occurs via the pressure hose with 1.6 mm diameter and 1.6 mm wall thickness. It is made of neoprene, which is and particularly suitable for abrasive fluids. The neoprene hose is pressed on the custom-made hose connector, which is a light conical cannula. This resists the high pressure of the pressure hose and prevents a disconnection.

For the suction hose a inner diameter of 1.6 mm is be to small. This would lead to high flow losses so that the hose pump cannot suck the viscous oil. That is why a 4 mm silicon hose is used for the suction hose. Silicon is also chemically totally inert and ensures that the hot oil is not contaminated by chemical reactions with the hose material.

Furthermore, a grounding cable and a cable for the contact potential are attached with a screw to the pot wall.

6.3.2 Test setup rocker arm / pivot ball

The contact situation between rocker arm and pivot ball specimen is pictured in figure 6.15. The rocker arm is fixed an the pivot ball rotates. The contact is drop lubricated, like in reality. This is realized by a rotating oil reservoir and thin bores in the pivot ball adapter. For a better inside view and to describe the function the test setup is illustrated in figure 6.16 as a section view of the CAD-model. In addition, a detailed view of the mounted specimens is illustrated in 6.17.

Figure 6.15: Contacting specimens: rocker arm against pivot ball

Figure 6.16: CAD design of test setup rocker arm / pivot ball (section view)

Figure 6.17: Mounted specimens: rocker arm / pivot ball (3D view)

Due to the modular system of the test setup almost the same parts can be used as in the previously described test setup rocker arm against push rod. Only the push rod adapter and push rod clamp have to be replaced by the pivot ball adapter and ball clamp.

In this case the rocker arm is the bottom specimen and is mounted on the pot. In figure 6.16 the rocker arm holder, rocker arm and pot is cut through a plane that is orthogonal to the cutting plane in figure 6.12.

The pivot ball is clamped with the ball clamp, which is similar to the push rod clamp but with a bigger bore diameter to fit the ball. Slightly more than half of the ball diameter must be enclosed by the ball clamp to ensure that the ball is clamped at the equator. This is illustrated in figure 6.17. The ball has to be positioned very precisely, because when too much of the ball is enclosed by the ball clamp, the ball clamp would contact the rocker arm. A shaft shoulder on the

pivot ball adapter with a smaller diameter than the ball ensures that the ball is positioned correctly relatively to the ball clamp.

In reality the rocker arm / pivot ball contact is drop lubricated. Because of the difficult access to the contact and the rotating upper parts this occurs via an oil reservoir. The oil flows from the hose pump through the pressure hose of neoprene to the cannula (see figure 6.18). The cannula drops the the oil into the rotating reservoir. The reservoir is mounted on the rotating shaft with a set screw. From the reservoir the oil flows through a transfer hose and via thin bores in the pivot ball adapter down to the ball clamp. The vertical oil bore in the pivot ball adapter is exactly positioned at the ball clamp slit, so that the escaping oil can drop through the ball clamp slit onto the contact between rocker arm and pivot ball. This only works when the upper specimen parts and the shaft do not rotate, otherwise the centrifugal forces would pull away the oil from the contact. Due to this issue, drop lubrication for this contact needs a start stop motion.

A pressure lubrication in this contact is also possible. This does not correspond to reality, but it was required to design the opportunity for possible future research projects. Pressure lubrication is realized by a thin bore through the shaft shoulder in the pivot ball adapter and a possibility to place a sealing ring between ball and shaft shoulder. This would be used if the ball was mounted as bottom specimen and then pressure lubricated through the pot. Therefore a bore through the ball would be necessary. It would also be possible to pressure lubricate the contact through the rocker arm and the bores in the rocker arm adapter and the pot. Therefore a shorter centering pin is inserted into the rocker arm.

Figure 6.18: Test setup rocker arm / pivot ball

6.3.3 Test setup pivot ball / pedestal

The contact between pivot ball and pedestal specimen is pictured in figure 6.19. Due to the modular system of the test setup almost the same parts are used as in the previously described test setup for pivot ball against rocker arm. Only the bottom specimen and adapters have to be replaced by the pedestal adapter and the pedestal. The CAD-design in section view is depicted in figure 6.20 and figure 6.21 shows the 3D view of the specimens and the specimen holders. The pedestal is cut in the middle and at the edge to fit into the pot (see figure 6.19). It is centered with a long centering pin through the middle of the socket to ensure collinearity of the specimens. The centering bore in the pedestal adapter and the length of the centering pin match in a way that the oil reservoir in the socket is not enlarged. The pedestal specimen is screwed on the pedestal adapter by an eccentric positioned screw between the two sockets on the pedestal half. This also prevents the specimen from rotation. The through bore for this screw is exactly in the middle between the two sockets. This allows to use both sockets per pedestal half for tests by offsetting the specimen. This is illustrated in figure 6.21. In this way all four sockets on a pedestal can be tested.

In this test setup the contact is mounted upside down compared to the real case to ensure a drop lubrication. The drop lubrication for this contact occurs similarly to the previously described test setup for pivot ball against rocker arm. The oil flows from the reservoir in the stop phase via a transfer hose and bores in the pivot ball adapter to the ball clamp, where it drops through the slit onto the contact.

Figure 6.19: Contacting specimens: pivot ball against pedestal

Figure 6.20: Test setup Pivot ball / Pedestal

Figure 6.21: Mounted specimens Pivot ball / Pedestal

6.4 Hose pump

As pump for the circulating lubrication systems like drop or pressure lubrication a hose pump is used. Thereby a continuous hose is inserted into the pump and rotating spring-loaded rolls squeeze the fluid through the hose into the wanted direction. This is a closed system and the lubricant does not contact any machine parts and cannot be contaminated. Furthermore the cleaning effort is minimized when changing the testing oil. This specific pump from *Watson Marlow 530U* (see figure 6.22) can be regulated down to a minimum rotational speed of 0.1 rpm and is suitable for thin hoses of 1.6 mm diameter to realize marginal lubrication. [85]

Figure 6.22: Hose pump *Watson Marlow 530U* [85]

6.5 Measured parameters

- Rotational speed [rpm]: It is measured by a rotary encoder on the rotational shaft and is directly proportional to the relative velocity of the contacting specimens.
- Axial load [kN]: It is measured by a load cell above the pneumatic air bellows and is directly proportional to the contact pressure.
- Oil bath temperature [°C]: It is measured by a bendable 1.5 mm thermoelement, which reaches through a thin bore at the top of the pot wall down into the oil bath. The measuring tip contacts the specimen adapter in a thin blind hole. This ensures that the oil bath temperature is always measured at the same spot and minimizes fluctuations due to convection.
- Contact temperature [°C]: Depending on the test setup, it is either measured by a 0.2 mm thermoelement or a 1.5 mm thermoelement. The 0.2 mm thermoelement is divided into its two measuring wires, which are welded together at the tip to form a loop. The temperature is measured at the welding point, which is in the middle of the loop. The loop encircles the specimen. This is mainly used for push rods, but also balls could be measured with this method. For rocker arms and pedestals the bendable 1.5 mm thermoelement is used. The tip contacts the specimen in a blind hole near the contact.
- Friction torque [Nm]: The tangential force of the friction contact is measured by a load cell, which contacts the fixed platform in a constant distance from the rotating axis. With the distance and the tangential force the friction torque can then be calculated.
- COF [-]: The coefficient of friction is calculated from the friction torque, the axial load and the contact radius.

- Contact potential [mV]: It is the electrical potential between the contacting surfaces and correlates with the fluid film thickness and non-conductive boundary layers. On the TE92 the contact potential is 50 mV when the specimens do not contact each other and is 0 mv when there is a metallic contact between the specimens.
- Wear [mg]: The gravimetric wear is the difference between weights before and after the test. The weights are measured by a very precise scale with a sensitivity of 10^{-5} g.

6.6 Test program

To ensure comparability tests have to be performed with the same test program. The test program can be programmed in the software *COMPEND*, which is the interface for the microprocessor controlled rotary tribometer TE92. For safety reasons and to protect the testing machine in any case of failure termination criteria can be implemented in *COMPEND* for every test program. These termination criteria are also called *alarms*. For example, a COF-alarm at 0.5 terminates the test when a $COF \geq 0.5$ is measured.

6.6.1 Calculation of valvetrain kinetics

For a first design of the test program the kinetics in the real valvetrain are calculated. With the given engine specs for the valve springs and the measured lengths of the rocker arms the resulting forces on the rocker arm at the valve, pivot ball and push rod are calculated.

The real engine tests are performed with an engine speed of 2800 rpm. This means that the cam shaft rotates with 1400 rpm, which leads to high inertia forces. For the inertia forces the reduced mass on the valve side m_{redV} without tappet (m_T) and push rod (m_{PR}) is needed, which is calculated with equation 3.16. Therefore also the mass moment of inertia is needed. Because of the complex shape of the rocker arm, it is very difficult to estimate the mass moment of inertia by approximation of simple geometric bodies. A practical approach was applied instead. The rocker arm was photographed and loaded into CATIA as a surface texture of a solid. Then the contour was sketched with splines and scaled to the right size with respect to some reference measurements. Then a solid was extruded from the sketch. This is pictured in figure 6.23. Once a realistic model of the rocker arm in CATIA exists, it the mass moment of inertia can easily be

calculated by CATIA. For further calculation the biggest rocker arm with the biggest mass moment of inertia was used, which is rocker arm number 2.

Figure 6.23: Realistic CAD-model of rocker arm 2 for computer-aided calculation of the mass moment of inertia

With the equations 3.13 - 3.15 described in subsection 3.2.3, the tappet lift, tappet velocity and tappet acceleration is calculated. By varying the rotation angle of the cam shaft φ the following diagrams in figure 6.24 are created.

Figure 6.24: Tappet lift s , tappet velocity v and tappet acceleration a as a function of the rotation angle of the cam shaft

With the given masses and the acceleration the inertia forces are calculated with equation 3.19. The highest wear is expected at the highest load and low velocity. A high velocity could support the forming of a load bearing lubrication film. The highest load occurs when the acceleration and thus the inertia forces reach their maximum. Because of that the relative velocity at a_{max} is relevant. The spring load is constant. A summary of the calculation results is listed in table 6.2.

According to these results the following test program was designed, which is illustrated in figure 6.25. The first design of the testing cycle is a start-stop-cycle which accelerates in 1 s to a peak of 1000 rpm, holds the speed for 2 s and decelerates to 0 rpm in 1 s again. Between the cycles is a 5 s stopping period. A start-stop-cycle was chosen because it is the most similar motion to the back and forth motion in the engine, which is realizable with a rotary tribometer. Furthermore, the drop lubrication needs stopping periods to work. Without stops, the centrifugal forces would pull the oil away from the contact.

Wear Contact	PR/RA	PB/RA	
Load due to spring	975	1625	N
Load due to inertia	500	834	N
Total load	1475	2459	N
Relative velocity at a_{max}	0.529	0.529	m/s
Rotational speed on tribometer	1059	1059	rpm

Table 6.2: Summary of valvetrain kinetics at engine speed 2800 rpm (PR = push rod, RA = rocker arm, PB = pivot ball)

Figure 6.25: First design of the start-stop-cycle for the test program

The engine oil temperature is 109°C, which is supposed to be the constant testing temperature. The heating of the oil is a relatively slow process and to minimize control fluctuations the first stage of the test program is 1 h only heating up the oil in standstill. Then a run in of 10 min under reduced load is necessary to smooth the contacting surfaces. As final stage the the start-stop-cycles perform the actual test. A schematic overview of the stages is illustrated in figure 6.26.

Figure 6.26: First design of the start-stop-cycle

6.6.2 Measurement diagrams

The control and measurement software of the tribometer can only create TSV-files (tab separated values). In the TSV-file a line for each data point is created. In all the tests in this thesis every 0.1 s a data point is created. This leads to a TSV-file with up to 100.000 lines. To evaluate those big data files a MATLAB script was written, which creates measurement diagrams. For better understanding of the measurement diagrams, they are explained in detail on the example of the test F014 (test ID) in figure 6.27 and table 6.3.

Figure 6.27: Explanation of measurement diagrams on the example of F014

Measurement quantity	Unit
Speed	[rpm]
Load	[kN]
Friction coefficient	[-]
Contact potential	[mV]
Oil bath temperature	[°C]
Contact temperature	[°C]

Table 6.3: Legend of measurement quantities

To perform one test per day, a test duration of less than 24 hours is preferred to ensure that the oil is cooled down when the specimens are dismantled and the next test is prepared. This means a few thousand cycles must fit in one diagram, which would make it impossible to receive an overview of the test progress. Therefore only the maximum values per cycle of all parameters listed in table 6.3 are plotted

into the measurement diagram. The peaks in the speed and contact temperature curve (upper right diagram in figure 6.27), which can be seen in all tests after F003, is due to a slow cycle to investigate the COF-speed behavior. Therefore a cycle with 1 min accelerating and 1 min decelerating is performed to create a precise plot of the COF in dependence of the speed (also called stribek-test). These slow cycles are performed every 100 cycles.

7 Experimental results

In the following chapter, the results of performed tests are presented. The tests are grouped into test packages and finally listed in a test matrix (see table 7.11) for an overview.

7.1 Test program optimization

Due to the principle of a rotary tribometer the rotation axis of the contacts of interest in the model is different to reality. A directly driven rotating start-stop cycle cannot be performed as quickly as the back and forth motion in the valvetrain. Consequently, the calculation of the test parameters speed and load based on a valvetrain only serves as a rough guide. Speed and load have to be optimized and adjusted to the testing machine to match the same wear mechanism like in reality (abrasive wear) and cause measurable wear in a moderate time (less than 24 h preferred). The test temperature is 109°C at all tests, like in reality.

In the following the tests F001 - F008 are described. The test parameters are listed in a table. The results are presented and the following action or optimization for the next test is explained. In addition, the measurement diagrams and relevant pictures of the optical analysis are depicted. For all tests the wear was measured gravimetrically and pictures of both specimens in zooms of 20x, 100x, 200x and 1000x were taken with the *Keyence VHX-5000* light microscope, but only selected pictures are attached in the following.

F001					
Top	Bottom	Lubrication	Oil	Load [kN]	Speed [rpm]
Rocker arm	Push rod	Pressure	Good oil	1.6	0-1000

Table 7.1: Test parameters of test F001

The first test F001 was performed with the parameters listed in table 7.1. Due to too high energy input the specimens heated up and friction welding occurred, see figure 7.1. As a consequence the maximum speed was reduced to 500 rpm for the next test. To further reduce energy input, the *hold-speed-stage* was removed. As the accelerating ramp of 1s was cannot be realized by the speed regulation, the acceleration ramp was adjusted to 5s.

Figure 7.1: F001: Friction welding

F002					
Top	Bottom	Lubrication	Oil	Load [kN]	Speed [rpm]
Rocker arm	Push rod	Pressure	Good oil	1.5	0-500

Table 7.2: Test parameters of test F002

The second test F002 was performed with the parameters listed in table 7.2. The test was canceled due to a broken suction hose (silicon). Consequently, the hose barb was deburred and the pump flow rate was reduced. Furthermore, the deceleration ramp was also set to 5s for a symmetric cycle (5s ac & dec).

F003

Top	Bottom	Lubrication	Oil	Load [kN]	Speed [rpm]
Rocker arm	Push rod	Pressure	Good oil	1.5	0-500

Table 7.3: Test parameters of test F003

Test F003 was performed with the parameters listed in table 7.3. The wear gravimetric wear was 0.89 mg at the rocker arm and -0.59 mg at the push rod. It is assumed that the push rod gains weight either due to material transfer or due to poor specimen cleaning. To minimize the influence of specimen cleaning and measuring fluctuations, the load was increased to cause more wear. The abrasive wear mechanism was matched on both specimens, as seen in figure 7.3. Furthermore, an unusual COF-speed characteristic for a lubricated contact (see stribek-curve in figure 3.10) was observed as seen in figure 7.2. To evaluate the COF-speed behavior, a slow cycle every 100cycles was introduced in F004 (see subsection 6.6.2). The overshooting of the speed to nearly 600 rpm is due to a slow regulation.

(b) Push rod 1000x**Figure 7.3:** F003: Optical analysis

F004					
Top	Bottom	Lubrication	Oil	Load [kN]	Speed [rpm]
Rocker arm	Push rod	Pressure	Good oil	2	0-500

Table 7.4: Test parameters of test F004

Test F004 was performed with the parameters listed in table 7.4. The wear at the rocker arm was 1.24 mg and -0.06 mg at the push rod. The test was canceled after 1100 min due a $\text{COF} > 0.5$ (see figure 7.4), which triggered the COF-alarm. The high COF lead to tempering colors, as seen in figure 7.5. As a consequence, the COF alarm was set to 0.9 to allow COF peaks and the maximum speed was reduced to 200 rpm to avoid tempering colors.

Figure 7.4: F004: Measurement diagram with COF peaks

Figure 7.5: F004: Tempering colors, rocker arm 20x

F005					
Top	Bottom	Lubrication	Oil	Load [kN]	Speed [rpm]
Pivot ball	Rocker arm	Drop	Good oil	3	0-200

Table 7.5: Test parameters of test F005

Test F005 was performed with the parameters listed in table 7.5. The test finished in 27.5 h and no tempering colors were observed (see figure 7.7b). Total seizure on the pivot ball occurred (see figure 7.7a) and an increase of COF and contact potential was observed (see diagram in figure 7.6). As a test duration of under 24 hours is preferred the cycle was shortened. This was realized by increasing the speed set point to 300 rpm, but start decelerating at 200 rpm. This leads to a quicker regulation and allows to set the ramp for acceleration and deceleration to 2s.

(b) Rocker arm 20x**Figure 7.7:** F005: Optical analysis

F006

Top	Bottom	Lubrication	Oil	Load [kN]	Speed [rpm]
Pivot ball	Rocker arm	Drop	Good oil	3	0-250

Table 7.6: Test parameters of test F006

Test F006 was performed with the parameters listed in table 7.6. The wear at the pivot ball was 0.03 mg and at the rocker arm 0.29 mg. The test finished in 21.3 h and 3500 cycles were performed. Due to the adjustments in speed regulations, the speed peaks up to 250 rpm. The abrasive wear mechanism was matched on both specimens (see figure 7.9) and a high contact potential was observed (see figure 7.8). It is assumed that this is due an unknown event at $t = 200min$ and followed by the built-up of a load bearing lubrication film, which would also explain the low wear. Except the low wear, these results seem good and this test is repeated with F007.

(b) Rocker arm 1000x**Figure 7.9:** F006: Optical analysis

F007

Top	Bottom	Lubrication	Oil	Load [kN]	Speed [rpm]
Pivot ball	Rocker arm	Drop	Good oil	3	0-250

Table 7.7: Test parameters of test F007

Test F007 was performed with the parameters listed in table 7.7. The wear at the pivot ball was 0.28 mg and 0.18 mg at the rocker arm. Despite exactly the same test parameters as in F006, the results of F007 are completely different. Total seizure occurred at the pivot ball (see figure 7.11a) and rough abrasive wear was observed at the rocker arm (see figure 7.11b). The contact potential was not that high as it was in F006 (see figure 7.10), which leads to the assumption that no load bearing lubrication film could be formed. If a load bearing lubrication film builds up, is evaluated by creating COF-speed diagrams, which are described in section 7.2.

Figure 7.10: F007: Measurement diagram

(a) Pivot ball 200x

(b) Rocker arm 1000x

Figure 7.11: F007: Optical analysis

F008

Top	Bottom	Lubrication	Oil	Load [kN]	Speed [rpm]
Rocker arm	Push rod	Pressure	Good oil	2.5	0-250

Table 7.8: Test parameters of test F008

Test F008 was performed with the parameters listed in table 7.8. The wear at the rocker arm was 0.62 mg and -0.29 mg at the push rod. The abrasive wear mechanism was matched on both specimens (see figure 7.13). For this contact the load was further reduced to 2kN to get closer to the calculated load.

(a) Rocker arm 1000x**(b)** Push rod 1000x**Figure 7.13:** F008: Optical analysis

Optimized test program

It was decided that for the following tests and methodology development the focus is on the contact rocker arm / push rod as it seems more stable than the contact pivot ball / rocker arm. 3500 cycles are performed, which takes 22 h in total. This allows to perform one test per day. A symmetrical cycle with an acceleration and deceleration ramp of 2 s is performed. As set point 300 rpm is programmed, but the machine starts decelerating to 0 rpm at the speed of 200 rpm. This leads to a quicker regulation. To to inertia and switching delays the speed peaks up to 250 rpm. The pump speed refers to a pressure hose with 1.6 mm inner diameter. The optimized test program is summarized in table 7.9 and the schematic cycle is illustrated in figure 7.14.

Load [kN]	Speed [rpm]	Temperature [°C]	Cycles [-]	Duration [h]	Pump speed [rpm]
2	0-250	109	3500	22	6

Table 7.9: Optimized test program

Figure 7.14: Optimized start-stop-cycle

7.2 Evaluation of COF-speed behavior

Due to the observation that F006 and F007 have totally different results in terms of the wear mechanism and the contact potential and COF, it is assumed that a lubricating film builds up in F006 and does not in F007. Obviously an event occurred at $t \sim 200min$ in F006, afterwards the COF peaked, stabilized at a higher level and the contact potential increased tremendously. In contrast, at F007 the COF stays at the same level (nearly same value before the event in F006) during the whole test and the contact potential does not build up.

After F003 the slower stribeck-profiles were performed and every 100. cycle measured. The creation of COF-speed diagrams was implemented into the *MATLAB* script. To get an overview of possible changes, all COF-speed diagrams of a test (every 100 cycles) are superpositioned in one diagram. Depending on the recorded moment the color of the curve shifts from red to blue, so red is the first and blue is the last curve. The start section is marked with dots. The *hook* at the start is due to an abrupt accelerating and regulation overshooting of the DC motor.

Figure 7.15: Superposition of COF-speed curves (red=first, blue=last)

As seen in figure 7.15, the COF-speed curves for both tests F006 and F007 have the same shape. Although the COF-value is different, the COF is independent of the speed in both tests. This means that no hydrodynamic friction regime occurs.

After F006 the above described diagrams are created for all tests and they all show a similar shape. Remarkable in F008 and other tests is that the COF slightly decreases with the run time. It is assumed that this is due to run in and surface smoothing effects.

7.3 Geometric conformity

With the optimized test cycle and the wear mechanism matched (abrasive wear) a first try of an oil ranking was performed. Therefore two tests each with good oil and poor oil were performed. F009 and F011 refer to the good oil, F012 and F014 refer to the poor oil. A comparison of the measurement diagrams is illustrated in figure 7.16.

Figure 7.16: F009-F014: First try oil ranking, measurement diagram comparison

It is noticed that despite the same test program and oil, different results were obtained. This means that improvements are needed for a better reproducibility. The optical analysis of the tests F009-F014 in figure 7.17 clearly shows that the contact area of rocker arms at tests F009 and F011 have a totally different shape. This was also noticed at tests F006 and F007, which are also performed with the same test parameters and the same oil. This leads to the assumption that the rocker arm sockets have a different geometry. The geometric difference results in different local surface pressures and different friction and wear behavior. Furthermore, figure 7.17 shows abrasive wear at the push rods of F011 and F014. F009 also has abrasive wear on the push rod and appears blue. It is assumed that the blue appearance is due to tribolayers. In F012 seizure and tempering colors occurred on both specimens.

Figure 7.17: F009-F014: First try oil ranking, optical analysis comparison

Contact area test

To check the geometry of the rocker arm sockets before the test, a contact area test was introduced. Therefore the rocker arm socket of a new specimen is painted with a permanent marker (better suitable than paint because of thin film thickness). Afterwards the rocker arm specimen is loaded with 0.2 kN against a push rod (always the same push rod is used as reference) and 3 revolutions are performed. This removes the permanent marker and visualizes the contact area. 10 Rocker arms were tested and the results are pictured in figure 7.18. The results of the contact area test prove that the rocker arm sockets have a different geometry. Only 5 out of 10 tested rocker arm sockets have a similar contact area. To improve reproducibility only specimens with similar contact areas are used for further testing.

Check reproducibility

To check the reproducibility two tests with poor oil and the rocker arms with the most similar contact area (RA003 and RA005 in figure 7.18) are performed. The results of these tests are pictured in figure 7.19. This confirms the assumption that the different contact area of the rocker arm sockets leads to different friction and wear behavior. This effect can be minimized with the introduced contact area test, which improves the reproducibility and will be performed for all future tests.

Figure 7.18: Contact area test of rocker arm sockets

Figure 7.19: F015 and F016: Check reproducibility

7.4 Used oil

As seen in figure 7.19, it was then possible to perform tests with a acceptable reproducibility but the wear was still too low for an oil ranking. Due to measurement fluctuations a higher wear was required to make meaningful statements in terms of lubricant effectiveness. To evaluate if it was possible to cause enough wear in 22 h test time, two tests with an used oil were performed. The used oil in the following tests is basically good reference oil, which was used in a real engine test for a run time of 200 h. Tests with used poor oil would be required to complete the test series, but unfortunately the used poor oil was not delivered as it was lost by the test laboratory where the engine test were performed.

Figure 7.20: F017 and F018: Tests with used oil (good oil, 200 h run time)

As seen in figure 7.20, in case of F017 the measurement diagram shows a few peaks in COF and contact temperature. The abrasive wear mechanism was matched for the rocker arm and the push rod. Significant wear was caused. For F018 the lubrication failed because the used oil clogged up the pressure hose and is not reliably pumpable. The results of the used oil tests in figure 7.20 prove that with this test rig it is possible to cause significant wear with the right wear mechanism (abrasive wear) in a moderate time (22 h).

7.5 Artificial oil aging

As fresh oil did not cause significant wear to make a meaningful statement in terms of oil effectiveness but used oil did indeed, an artificial oil aging was tried. This means to add substances to fresh oil, which occur in used oil. Analysis show that used oil also contains particles and soot. In the following certain oil blends with fresh oil and particles or soot were created and blended with a magnetic stirrer, which is pictured in figure 7.21. In a magnetic stirrer the stirrer is driven by a rotating magnetic field outside the container. The advantage of this principle is that only the stirrer contacts the oil and a contamination with unwanted substances can be prevented.

Figure 7.21: Magnetic stirrer for blending (*IKA RCT basic*) [86]

7.5.1 Abrasive particles Arizona Dust

It is assumed that particles result from other tribological contacts in the engine, contaminate the circulating oil and cause abrasive wear at the ball/socket-contacts in the valvetrain. To evaluate this hypothesis abrasive particles were added to fresh oil (poor oil). As abrasive particles the standardized (SAE J726 and ISO 12103-1) test dust Arizona Dust was used. It is chemically inert and mainly consists of silicon dioxide. The exact chemical composition is listed in table 7.10a. There are 4 grades of Arizona Dust, which differ in particle size. According to the oil analysis of used oil the A1 Ultrafine grade is best suitable for a surrogate of abrasive particles. The particle size distribution is listed in table 7.10b. [87] [88] [89]

Chemical	Weight percent	Size [μm]	% less than
SiO_2	68-76 %	0.97	3.0-5.0
Al_2O_3	10-15 %	1.38	7.0-10.0
Fe_2O_3	2-5 %	2.75	23.0-27.0
Ca_2O	2-5 %	5.50	65.0-69.0
K_2O	2-5 %	11.00	95.5-97.5
Na_2O	2-4 %	22.00	100.0
MgO	1-2 %		
TiO_2	0.5-1 %		

(a) Chemical composition [88]

(b) Particle size distribution by volume for A1 Ultrafine [88]

Table 7.10: Physical properties of Arizona Dust

For the first test series 0.085 g Arizona Dust A1 Ultrafine grade was added to 250 ml poor oil, which is equivalent to 0.04 wt% (weight percent). This mixing ratio is suggested by Schiffer J. in [89].

Figure 7.22: F019: Poor oil + Arizona Dust 0.04 wt%

The results of F019 in figure 7.22 show that the COF and the contact temperature are significantly increased in comparison to tests F015 and F016 without abrasive

particles but the wear did not increase. In the optical analysis mainly grooves are seen with a few cracks and breakouts. This means that mainly abrasive wear occurs and locally fatigue or adhesive seems to occur.

A repeat test (F020) was performed, which can be seen in figure 7.23. In F020 the COF is extremely high from the beginning and the test was canceled after a short run time due to a COF-alarm of 0.9. The gravimetric wear is high but the wear mechanism does not match.

Figure 7.23: F020: Poor oil + Arizona Dust 0.04 wt%

As F019 and F020 have totally different results, it was assumed that probably the added abrasive particles did not reach the contact in F019. So another repeat test F021 was performed, which results are pictured in figure 7.24. Unfortunately the silicon suction hose broke at $t = 800min$ and seizure occurred. But also in F021 the extreme COF-peaks can be seen at the beginning but then the COF stabilizes at a relative low level of 0.12. According to equation 3.6, rolling abrasion is not probable in this case, which means that the breakouts have another cause.

Figure 7.24: F021: Poor oil + Arizona Dust 0.04 wt%

It is assumed that 0.04 wt% is too aggressive for this contact and a test series with 0.02 wt % was performed. Therefore 0.0425 g Arizona Dust A1 Ultrafine was added to 250 ml poor oil.

The first test performed with 0.02 wt% Arizona Dust is F022, which is pictured in figure 7.25. No COF-peaks and abrasive wear with some breakouts occur in F022. Black oil deposits and metallic deposits are noticed on the rocker arm. Remarkable is that the gravimetric wear is almost equal to F019 (0.04 wt%).

A repeat test F023 with 0.02 wt% was performed, which is pictured in 7.26. Again no COF-peaks occur and the wear mechanism is mainly abrasive wear with some breakouts. Also here metallic deposits are noticed. No significant wear was caused.

Figure 7.25: F022: Poor oil + Arizona Dust 0.02 wt%

Figure 7.26: F023: Poor oil + Arizona Dust 0.02 wt%

7.5.2 Soot surrogate Carbon Black

As neither with 0.02 wt% nor 0.04 wt% abrasive particles no significant wear was caused, it was assumed that adding abrasive particles is not expedient for simulating similar results as with used oil. As used oil contains abrasive particles and soot, the following test series is performed with artificially aged oil by adding soot surrogate Carbon Black to fresh oil.

As described in 3.4.8 soot surrogate Carbon Black interacts with ZDDP and abrades ZDDP films as rapidly as they form, which leads to a high rate of corrosive-abrasive wear. When ZDDP and Carbon Black is present much higher wear occurs as when either ZDDP or Carbon black is absent. [73]-[77]

As soot surrogate Carbon Black P1011 was used, as this was already available in the laboratory. Referring to the studies described in 3.4.8 5 wt% Carbon Black were added to fresh oil. Calculating with a density of Carbon Black of 1.7 g/cm^3 and an oil density of 0.86 g/cm^3 , 5 wt% equals 11.6 g Carbon Black added to 268 ml fresh oil, which leads to total volume of 275 ml. This oil blend was then mixed with a magnetic stirrer for 4 hours at a rotational speed of 600 rpm.

Figure 7.27: F024: Poor oil + Carbon Black 5 wt%

The first test F024 was performed with poor oil and 5 wt% Carbon Black. As seen in figure 7.27, for the first time significant wear was caused on this test setup

without seizure. Although the abrasive grooves are rougher than in F019, the wear mechanism was matched and the same discolorations can be seen. Referring to the ZDDP film built up described in figures 3.28 and 3.29, it is assumed that the brown discolorations is iron sulphide (FeS) and the blue ones are iron (Fe) or zinc (Zn) phosphates. Also the measurement diagram is similar to the used (good) oil test F017 with fluctuations and sharp peaks of COF and contact temperature. The fact that the used oil in F017 is originally good oil would explain the higher wear in F024, which is performed with poor oil and soot surrogate.

Test F024 provided meaningful results, which match the theory. To reinforce those results a repeat test F025 was performed. Unfortunately the speed regulation of the TE92 failed again at this test and the specimens were totally destroyed. Because only two sets of specimens were left at this time, it was decided to use them for two tests with good oil and carbon black to prove that the test setup is suitable for oil screening and differences in terms of oil effectiveness can be shown.

Figure 7.28: F026: Good oil + Carbon Black 5 wt%

Test F026 was performed with good oil and 5 wt% Carbon Black and the results are pictured in 7.28. Significant wear was caused, but not as much as with poor oil in F024. The wear on the push rod only differs 0.01 mg from the wear in F017 with used good oil. The abrasive grooves are similar to F024 and also rougher than with used good oil in F017, but the general wear mechanism was matched.

7.6 Test matrix

For an overview of the performed tests a test matrix is listed in table 7.11. All tests except F005 - F007 (rocker arm against pivot ball) are performed with rocker arm against push rod and the optimized test program described in table 7.9 and figure 7.14. The wear of canceled or failed tests is not comparable and is not listed in the test matrix.

Test package	Test ID	Oil	Addition	wt [%]	Wear RA [mg]	Wear PR [mg]
Test program optimization 7.1	F001	Good oil			<i>canceled</i>	
	F002	Good oil			<i>canceled</i>	
	F003	Good oil			0.89	-0.58
	F004	Good oil			1.24	-0.06
	F005	Good oil			<i>no data</i>	
	F006	Good oil			0.29	0.03 PB
	F007	Good oil			0.18	0.28 PB
	F008	Good oil			0.62	-0.29
First try oil ranking 7.3	F009	Good oil			1.15	0.33
	F011	Good oil			0.45	4.75
	F012	Poor oil			<i>canceled</i>	
	F014	Poor oil			0.17	0.43
Check reproducibility 7.3	F015	Poor oil			0.65	0.49
	F016	Poor oil			0.13	0.24
Used oil 7.4	F017	Used good oil			1.32	3.99
	F018	Used good oil			<i>canceled</i>	
Abrasive particles 7.5.1	F019	Poor oil	+ AD	0.04	0.62	0.30
	F020	Poor oil	+ AD	0.04	<i>canceled</i>	
	F021	Poor oil	+ AD	0.04	<i>canceled</i>	
	F022	Poor oil	+ AD	0.02	0.57	0.26
	F023	Poor oil	+ AD	0.02	0.03	0.18
Soot surrogate 7.5.2	F024	Poor oil	+ CB	5	3.49	5.12
	F026	Good oil	+ CB	5	2.58	4.00

Table 7.11: Test matrix (RA = Rocker arm, PR = Push rod, PB = Pivot ball, AD = Arizona Dust, CB = Carbon Black)

8 Discussion

In this chapter the experimental results of chapter 7 are discussed. First, the engine and model tests are compared. Then the observed influences of various parameters are presented and conclusions or assumptions are explained.

8.1 Comparison of engine and model tests

A comparison of engine and model tests shows that with the developed test rig it is possible to match the same abrasive wear mechanism as in the engine (see figure 8.1). The grooves caused by engine tests in figure 8.1a are rougher and not continuous. It is assumed that this is due to the pushing-back-and-forth motion in the engine. Due to the principle of a rotary tribometer, a consistent rotation occurs in model tests.

(a) Engine test (PR)

(b) Model test (F011, PR)

Figure 8.1: Comparison of engine and model tests

8.2 Influence of speed and load

Based on a calculation of speed and load in a real valvetrain, these parameters were varied in order to match the same abrasive wear mechanism as in the engine application. The tests showed that high maximum speed during tests leads to a high energy input and friction heat development, which results in tempering

colors, or even friction welding (figure 8.2a). Too much load leads to seizure, and high adhesive wear occurs (figure 8.2b). Only with the right combination of speed and load the abrasive wear mechanism can be matched (figure 8.1b).

Figure 8.2: Influence of speed and load on the tribological behavior

8.3 Influence of geometric conformity

During the first tests a high scatter of the tribometric results was observed although the test parameters were the same. The optical analysis of worn rocker arm sockets showed that the shape of contacting areas differs (figure 8.3). A contact area test whereby unused rocker arms are tested against the same push rod shows that the sockets of the rocker arms do not all have the same geometry. A small contact area leads to a higher local load than a big contact area (figure 8.4a,b). It is assumed that a non-circumferential contact area (figure 8.4c) leads to a wedge effect, which supports the build-up of a lubricating oil film. For meaningful test results and improved reproducibility only similar contact areas can be compared, which requires a contact area test before every screening-test.

Figure 8.3: Different contact areas of worn rocker arm sockets

Figure 8.4: Selected contact area tests

8.4 Influence of abrasive particles

The influence of abrasive particles in the oil was tested by adding Arizona Dust to fresh oil. Arizona Dust is mainly silicon dioxide, which is harder than the steel used and chemically inert. The ultrafine grade was used with 65% of the particles smaller than 5.5 μm and 100% smaller than 22 μm .

The test results (table 8.1) show a significant increase in COF due to abrasive particles. With 0.04 wt% of Arizona Dust the COF increased to 0.22 in F019. In the following tests F020 and F021 the COF peaked to very high values at the beginning of the test, which led to seizure and high wear. Although a high wear was caused in these tests, the gravimetric wear is not representative because it is caused by a different wear mechanism than in the engine. As F020 and F021 show similar results, it is assumed that in F019 the particles did not reach the the contact as they did in F020 and F021. Furthermore, it is assumed that the high COF peaks at the beginning of F020 and F021 are due to an accumulation of particles during the heating stage. While heating up, the pump is running and the specimens contact each other, but without rotation. As 0.04 wt% seems to be too aggressive, the abrasive particle concentration was reduced to 0.02 wt%. The test results with 0.02 wt% also show a significant increase in the COF, but not as high as with 0.04 wt%, and extremely high peaks at the beginning of the tests did not occur. It is concluded that abrasive particles increase the COF depending on their concentration. At low concentrations, abrasive wear occurs but does not significantly increase the gravimetric wear in comparison to tests without abrasive particles. Above a certain concentration, abrasive particles lead to seizure and high wear.

Furthermore, the abrasive particles have an effect on the wear mechanism as breakouts occur at both concentrations in addition to abrasive wear (figure 8.5a). Referring to the wear mode map and the calculated severity, rolling abrasion is

unlikely, which means the breakouts have another cause. As cracks occur near the breakouts too, it seems that these breakouts occur due to local fatigue. But as local fatigue is improbable under these testing conditions (short duration), it is assumed that the breakouts occur due to local adhesive wear. Metallic deposits are noticed near the oil entry (figure 8.5b). A hypothesis for this phenomenon is that the metallic debris from the breakouts contaminates the circulating oil and attaches to the contacting surfaces due to high local pressure. Figure 8.5b also shows that the surface under the metallic deposits was exposed to abrasive wear before. This means that the deposits occur at a later stage of the test, which would support this hypothesis and the assumption that the breakouts result from fatigue. This could also explain the fact that the wear does not significantly increase despite breakouts.

Although abrasive particles lead to a higher COF and local fatigue wear, it is assumed that they are not primarily responsible for the high wear and consequent failure of the investigated ball/socket-contacts.

Test ID	Oil	Addition	wt [%]	max. COF [-]	Wear RA [mg]	Wear PR [mg]
F015	Poor oil			0.16	0.65	0.49
F016	Poor oil			0.15	0.13	0.24
F019	Poor oil	+ AD	0.04	0.22	0.62	0.30
F020	Poor oil	+ AD	0.04	0.90	(4.98)	(14.70)
F021	Poor oil	+ AD	0.04	0.75	(3.94)	(11.99)
F022	Poor oil	+ AD	0.02	0.18	0.57	0.26
F023	Poor oil	+ AD	0.02	0.19	0.03	0.18

Table 8.1: Tests without and with Arizona Dust (AD) in different concentrations (wear values in () is are due to seizure).

(a) Abrasive wear with cracks and breakouts

(b) Metallic deposits at oil entry

Figure 8.5: F023: Optical analysis of selected rocker arms

8.5 Influence of soot

The influence of soot in the oil was tested by adding 5 wt% soot surrogate Carbon Black P1011 to fresh oil. With Carbon Black (CB) significant wear was caused (table 8.2). Consequently, it is assumed that soot is a wear promoter in the investigated valvetrain. Furthermore, the wear caused with poor oil + CB is significantly higher than the wear caused with good oil + CB, which matches the results of engine tests. This would prove that with this test procedure an oil ranking can be created, but must be confirmed by further tests.

Test ID	Oil	Addition	wt [%]	Wear RA [mg]	Wear PR [mg]
F009	Good oil			1.15	0.33
F017	Used good oil			1.32	3.99
F024	Poor oil	+ CB	5	3.49	5.12
F026	Good oil	+ CB	5	2.58	4.00

Table 8.2: Influence of Carbon Black (CB)

The measurement diagrams of used oil and fresh oil with Carbon Black are similar to a general fluctuation and sharp peaks of COF and contact temperature (figure 8.6). The fact that the measurement diagram of used good oil seems more stable could be due to higher reactivity or a higher tendency of agglomeration of the soot surrogate P1011 than engine soot.

(a) F017: Used good oil

(b) F026: Good oil + 5 wt% CB

Figure 8.6: Comparison of measurement diagrams

There is also a big similarity in the surface analysis (figure 8.8). Both surfaces in figure 8.6b and 8.6c show abrasive wear with brown and blue discolorations. Referring to the structure of ZDDP pads (figure 8.7), it is assumed that the brown layers are iron or zinc sulphide (FeS/ZnS) and the blue layers are iron or zinc

phosphates. As the surface of test F015 without Carbon Black appears completely blue (figure 8.8a), it is concluded that here the ZDDP pads are fully formed but cannot be formed up when Carbon Black is present (figure 8.8b,c). This would confirm the findings of previous studies ([74]-[77]) which showed that Carbon Black and ZDDP interact, which leads to a corrosive-abrasive wear mechanism and higher wear than in the absence of one of these due to immature tribopad detachment.

Figure 8.7: Schematic structure of ZDDP pads and composition [66]

(a) F015: Poor oil, mature ZDDP pads

(b) F017: Used good oil, immature ZDDP pads

(c) F024: Poor oil + CB, immature ZDDP pads

Figure 8.8: Comparison of surfaces

9 Summary

A model test setup for three different ball/socket-contacts in a valvetrain was developed. With its modular structure it is possible to perform tests with specimens cut out from real parts and vary positions, lubrication and motion. In total, 26 methodology tests were performed.

In the first test series a suitable test program and the parameters speed and load were empirically determined. The tests showed that high load leads to seizure and high speed leads to friction welding. Only with the right balance of speed and load the abrasive wear mechanism was able to be matched which also occurs in engine tests.

The second test series showed that rocker arms have scatters in geometry, which has a big influence on the friction and wear behavior. By introducing a contact area test the reproducibility was improved.

Tests with used oil proved that with this test setup it is possible to cause significant wear in a moderate time of 22 h which allows to perform one test per day for future tribosystem-screening tests.

Tests with fresh oil caused too low wear to make meaningful statements in terms of oil effectiveness. Therefore, the last test series was performed with artificially aged oil. Arizona Dust ultrafine, which is mainly silicon dioxide, was added to fresh oil in different mixing ratios of 0.04 and 0.02 wt% to act as abrasive particles. It was shown that depending on their concentration abrasive particles increase the COF, which can lead to seizure, but do not increase mild abrasive wear. Breakouts were observed at the worn surfaces in addition to abrasive wear. As the theoretical criterion for rolling abrasion is not fulfilled, it is assumed that these breakouts occur due to local adhesive wear because fatigue is improbable under these conditions. Because the worn surfaces with breakouts also show metallic depositions at the oil entry, it is assumed that the debris from the breakouts contaminates the circulating oil and attaches at the oil entry due to high local pressure.

It is concluded that abrasive particles are not primarily responsible for the high wear in the investigated contacts, so tests were performed with 5 wt% of a soot surrogate Carbon Black P1011. The test results show that the wear significantly

increases due to the soot surrogate Carbon Black and immature ZDDP-pads on worn surfaces were observed (needs to be confirmed by EDX) in addition to abrasive grooves. This confirms the conclusion of previous studies that ZDDP and soot interact, which leads to high corrosive-abrasive wear by abrading immature ZDDP-pads.

To evaluate the suitability of this test procedure for future oil-screening tests, which allow to create an oil ranking and find the best suitable oil for this application, tests with a good and a poor reference oil were performed. The poor reference oil causes more wear than the good reference oil, as is known from engine tests. This finding validates the set up for oil-screening tests, but must be confirmed by further tests. In table 9.1 the final test procedure is summarized to facilitate the repetition for further confirmation and oil-screening tests.

Test setup	Test rig	TE92
	Top specimen	Rocker arm
	Bottom specimen	Push rod
	Lubrication	Pressure
Test program	Load	2 kN
	Speed	0-250 rpm
	Motion	Start-stop-cycle
	Details	2s ramp ac & dec, 5s stop
	Temperature	109 °C
	Cycles	3500
	Duration	22 h
Lubrication system	Pump model	Watson Marlow 530U
	Pump speed	6 rpm
	Pressure hose	Neoprene $d_i \times s = 1.6 \times 1.6$ mm
	Suction hose	Silicone $d_i = 4$ mm
	Oil Volume	80 ml
Artificial oil aging	Soot surrogate	Carbon Black P1011
	Soot content	5 wt%
	Mixing suggestion	11.6g CB + 268 ml = 275ml
	Mixing duration	4 h
	Speed magnetic stirrer	600 rpm

Table 9.1: Final test procedure for future oil screening

10 Outlook

Further tests with poor and good reference oil with soot surrogate should be performed to confirm the suitability for oil-screening tests. In addition, tests with other oils are suggested and their results have to be compared with engine tests. Furthermore, SEM and EDX analyses must be performed to confirm assumptions based on analysis with light microscopes. Especially the discolorations of presumed immature ZDDP-pads and the metallic deposits have to be confirmed by EDX-analysis.

The influence of the geometric conformity was indeed able to be reduced by introducing a contact area test, but it seems that it has not been totally eliminated yet. For further reduction it is suggested that future contact area tests are performed with both specimens push rod and rocker arm. By measuring the oil flow through the pressure hose it could be determined if the contact seals or not. The effects of abrasive particles require further investigation. It has to be ensured that the abrasive particles really reach the contact. It is proposed to realize this by grinding radial lubrication grooves into the rocker arm socket.

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